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Design and evaluation of digital techniques for audio
amplification

By

David Brian Winter

B.Eng. (Hons) Electronic Systems and Information
Engineering

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PREFACE

This report describes project work carried out in the School of Engineering at Sheffield Hallam University between October 2000 to May 2001.

The submission of the report is in accordance with the requirements for the award of the degree of B.Eng. (Hons) Electronic Systems and Information Engineering under the auspices of the University.

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ABSTRACT

The process of uniformly sampled pulse width modulation (UPWM), with reference to digital audio amplification, is investigated as an alternative to a digital to analogue converter (DAC).

The whole process of digital amplification design is discussed, resulting in minimal harmonics in the audio band and 16-bit signal to noise specification.

For realisation of 16-bit performance, emphasis is placed upon the need for oversampling, noise shaping and linearisation.

The processes are expressed analytically in order to solve the technical difficulties associated with the operational frequency of the output stage.

The S/PDIF interface is analysed to show the requirements of the pulse code modulation media.

A flexible MATLAB - SIMULINK digital amplifier model is developed to allow easy evaluation of the concepts.

The design of a H-Bridge D-class amplifier, demodulator and a PCM to PWM mapped system is shown.

Finally, a proposed solution is expressed to show how a practical implementation could be designed and stored.

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Nomenclature

AC – Alternating Current
A/D – Analogue to Digital
AES – Audio Engineering Society
CD – Compact Disc
CS – Channel Select (start of block sequence in S/PDIF).
D/A – Digital to Analogue
DC – Direct Current
DSP – Digital Signal Processing
ECL – Emitter Coupled Logic
FIR – Finite Impulse Response
FFT – Fast Fourier Transform
FPGA – Field Programmable Gate Array
 f_s - Sampling Frequency
GUI – Graphical User Interface
LSB – Least Significant Bit
MOSFET – Metal Oxide Semiconductor Field Effect Transistor
MSB – Most Significant Bit
NPWM – Natural Pulse Width Modulation
NS – Noise Shaping
NTF – Noise Transfer Function
OLRCK – Output Left Right Clock
OSR – Oversampling Ratio
PC – Personal Computer
PCM – Pulse Code Modulation
PNPWM – Pseudo-natural Pulse Width Modulation.
PWM – Pulse Width Modulation
RCBL – Receiver Channel Status Block
SDOUT – Serial Audio Data Out
STF – Signal Transfer Function
UPWM – Uniform Pulse Width Modulation

1. INTRODUCTION

Title of project: Design and evaluation of digital techniques for audio amplification

1.1 Technical overview

For many years now class 'A' and class 'A-B' analogue audio amplifiers have dominated the market place for amplifying the analogue output of a digital source [7,19]. In particular class 'A' amplifiers which are inherently the most linear (least amount of distortion) are extremely in-efficient (~50% maximum) due to bias currents flowing in the output devices at all times [18].

The in-efficiency by-product of class-A amplification results in large, bulky heatsinks that dominate the chassis.

In order to combat these problems there is a compromise; class 'A-B' amplification produces good linearity with modest power usage [18,19]. However being a compromise, it is by no means a perfect alternative to the engineering problem.

The digital domain has been used very successfully in the last few decades in the form of Pulse Coded Modulation (PCM) signal sources.

The next logical step would be to take advantage of this media in order to utilise the higher signal to noise ratios and lower distortion offered by today's digital media [11,15,16].

The novel approach aims to delve into the digital domain in order to process and amplify a digital signal (processed from the output of a digital PCM source).

Traditional methods convert the PCM signal to a continuous form via digital to analogue conversion. The signal is then amplified using analogue technology.

The fundamental approach to the digital amplifier concept could then, be seen as a power digital to analogue conversion [15,21].

To date, the exploitation of digital amplification in the commercial world has been non-existent; except at the very extremes of the audio industry, courtesy of Tact Audio [14]. This is due to several problematic technicalities that shall be discussed in the forthcoming chapters.

Several researchers and companies have contributed to this concept in order to try to realise a solution via the pulse width modulation (PWM) process [2,4,5,6,7,14,15,21,34]. The PWM process has been used in the past for applying gain to an analogue signal, in the form of class-D amplification. This modulation scheme and switching technology allows digital or analogue modulation and thus the basis of the whole project.

Summary of the possible advantages of a digital amplifier over an analogue equivalent:

- A theoretical higher level of basic linearity [7,14,41].
- Higher signal to noise ratio and lower distortion [2,4,6,7,14,15,21,34,41].
- Greater efficiency [7,11,19,41].
- Reductions in cost due to the use of smaller heatsinks/general cooling.
- Reductions in power supply complexity [7,14]

1.2 Project Overview

The project's aim is to investigate and research the modulation and switching techniques that have already been partially researched to produce digital audio amplification. The outcome is to find out the reasons why, major manufactures to date, have not commercially produced a solution based upon digital amplification technology.

Since the compact disc (CD) is the most common of all PCM sources [17], the project shall be based around this system.

CD is a PCM system that offers 16-bit resolution and a sampling frequency of 44.1kHz.

The project begins with chapter 2, discussing the hardware interface (S/PDIF) of a CD player, followed by the theoretical concepts involved with resolving the problems of the modulation process. This includes the linearisation of the various non-linear PWM schemes, the reduction in word size to overcome the bit-rate problem using oversampling and noise shaping, class-D amplification and the demodulation process.

In chapter 3, an entire theoretical digital amplifier system is modelled in software using MATLAB and the MATLAB-SIMULINK system. This utilises a CD specified input, oversampling, linearisation, noise-shaping, Uniform Pulse Width Modulation (UPWM) topologies, class-D amplification and demodulation.

The hardware interface of a CD player is examined using a hardware interface board, provided kindly by Crystal Semiconductors.

A direct PCM to PWM conversion, H-Bridge D-class amplifier and demodulator is shown, designed in Mentor Graphics.

This is subsequently developed to include the practical S/PDIF data frame. The data frame is implemented into the PCM to PWM conversion process, to show extraction of the data.

A Simple PWM conversion process is shown using PSPICE.

A proposed practical implementation is shown to enable the complete realisation of the concept, using available technology.

Chapter 4 summarises the results, followed by an evaluation, critical analysis and costing evaluation in chapters 5, 6 and 7 respectively.

Finally, a simple critical comparison of a traditional DAC/analogue amplifier combination with the derived Digital Amplifier are discussed in chapter 8, along with suggestions for further research.

1.3 Preliminary Research

Background reading and research was required in order to successfully understand the principles behind a digital audio amplifier, as it is a relatively novel approach.

Several companies have been researching into the techniques of digital amplification including (all were contacted via email):

Neofidelity, Audiologic, Texas Instruments, Cirrus Logic, Tripath Technology and Tact audio [ψ].

Note that no major hi-fi manufacturers are present in the list.

Audiologic replied saying that:

“Unfortunately, our work is proprietary and I can’t send any information on our latest developments”

Cirrus Logic replied saying that the email had been forwarded to the head of the digital amplifier project, a Dr. Skip Taylor. A reply from Dr. Skip Taylor concluded that the final design would not be completed until early August 2001.

The other companies declined to reply.

An email was sent to a researcher named Wayne Padgett who produced a technical paper [21], along with Erik Bresch. He was unable to help as he had lost contact with Erik Bresch (for whom I tried to contact and failed).

Tact audio [14] have a digital amplifier called the ‘Millenium’ and as predicted it boasts efficiency and specification to put class ‘A’ amplifiers to shame, with a claimed signal to noise ratio of over 100dB, an efficiency of 89% at harmonic distortion levels less than 0.05% at full power. This is at a price of 10,000\$ is rather expensive but does illustrate the potential of using a PCM to PWM /D-Class amplifier technique.

Whilst browsing the internet a company called Pulsustech [16] was found which produces a 24-bit 192Khz PCM to PWM converter - PS9604 (note also 16-bit, 44.1Khz, i.e. CD player compatible). This company had been contacted to find out the cost of the product and was found to be not actually available until July 2001.

Audiologic [15] advised searching for patents issued to a John Melanson and Peter Craven. These were searched for at the British and American patents office. It was found that the patents were issued to the development of a digital amplifier for hearing aids.

2. Theoretical Background

2.1 Chapter overview

The chapter introduces the digital PCM interface of a CD player. The concepts involved in the PWM process and Class D-amplifiers are examined. Furthermore, the benefits of oversampling and noise shaping are explained in detail, along with the addition of dither. PWM linearity problems will be identified, along with a brief discussion of the feedback mechanism for which analogue class-D amplifiers rely up on for uniformity. PCM to PWM conversion will be described in depth, finally followed with the demodulation process and the testing and measurement concepts utilised in the audio industry.

2.2 Hardware Interfacing

The AES IEC958 S/PDIF interface [12,13] is a digital serial communication line, that is often fitted to CD players and other digital media.

The S/PDIF standard is bi-phase encoded to allow a receiver to extract a clock from the data, as shown in figure 2.1.

Figure 2.1 (a) Bi-phase mark encoding, (b) basic implementation

2.2.1 Blocks, Frames and Sub-frame format

An audio sample is placed in a structure known as a sub-frame, shown in figure 2.2. The sub-frame consists of 4 bits of preamble (sync bits), 8 bits of auxiliary data, a 16-bit audio sample, 3 bits called validity, user and channel status, followed by a parity bit. The sub-frame is transmitted LSB (bit0) to the MSB (bit31).

Figure 2.2 32-bit sub-frame format for a CD player

The auxiliary bits are set to all zeros for CD. The validity bit is usually low, enabling the data to be D/A converted. The user bit is undefined so is set to zero but the channel status bit consists of a single bit per sub-frame assembled in blocks of 192 bits in 24*8 bytes. The start of channel status has a unique pre-amble sync pattern, occurring in the first sub-frame within frame 0. The channel data is updated every:

$$(1 * \text{no. of frames}) / f_s = (1 / 44.1 \text{e}3) * 192 = 4.3532 \text{ ms, for CD.}$$

Equation 2.1

Where f_s = sampling frequency (Hz)

The channel status bits consist of format information including sampling frequency, pre-emphasis, copy right protection, type of audio and consumer/professional interface used amongst other things.

For an in depth coverage on the full standard, see the official AES IEC958 S/PDIF standard which can be bought from the Audio Engineering Society directly or alternatively information can be found in [12,13].

Finally the parity bit generates even parity and thus can detect an odd number of transmission errors in a subframe.

Error detection based on the parity bit is performed in one of two ways: -

1. At the data layer, by testing the parity bit in each sub-frame

- At the electrical layer, by verifying properties of the bi-phase mark signal for time slots 4 to 31 and the specific patterns of the pre-ambls for time slots 0 to 3.

A frame is made up of 2 sub-frames, the first being the left channel, followed by the right channel. A block is made up of 192 frames. The format for the frame sequence is shown in figure 2.3.

Figure 2.3 Frame/block format

The Preamble separates the start of the block (channel status-CS), the left and right channel using different sync patterns. The basic structures are illustrated in figure 2.4.

Figure 2.4 Preamble sync patterns

Quick calculations show that as the sampling frequency (f_s) is 44.1×10^3 Hz, the bit rate equates to:

$$(f_s * (\text{left and right subframe}))$$

$$44.1 \times 10^3 \times 32 \times 2 = 2.8224 \text{ MHz}$$

2.3 Oversampling and Dithered Noise Shaping Quantisers

In order to effectively design a digital amplifier, physics dictates that the bit rate needs to be subsequently reduced, as will be seen later on in the report.

Due to a reduction in bit-rate, the loss of signal to noise ratio (SNR) will no doubt be encountered. To reduce this effect, both oversampling and noise shaping can be used.

2.3.1 Oversampling

To begin with, the basics of a CD player will be looked at, in order to help explain the principles of oversampling.

The quantisation step size of a 16-bit CD player of peak-to-peak output of 1 volt is:

$$Q = \text{Full scale voltage} / (2^n - 1) = 1 / (2^{16} - 1) = 15.26 \mu\text{V}$$

Equation 2.2

The quantisation error, due to quantisation itself is half the quantisation interval.

$$Q_e = 0.5 * Q = 7.63 \mu\text{V}$$

Equation 2.3

Since a sinusoid is quantised, the quantised signal power is:

$$P_s = ((Q * 2^n) / (2 * \sqrt{2}))^2 = Q^2 * (2^{2n} / 8)$$

Equation 2.4

However, when oversampling is used it can be shown that the quantisation noise power is reduced, where:

$$P_e = (2 * f_o * Q^2) / (12 * f_s) = (Q^2 / 12) * (1 / \text{OSR})$$

OSR = Oversampling ratio,
 f_o = Nyquist frequency (Hz),
 f_s = Sampling frequency (Hz)

Equation 2.5

i.e. As the total quantisation noise power is distributed over a larger frequency range, the noise power in the audible band (0 to f_o).

The resulting signal to noise ratio for a standard CD player is:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SNR} &= 10 * \log(P_s / P_e) = 10 \log(1.5 * 2^{2n}) + 10 * \log(\text{OSR}) \\ &= 6.02 * n + 1.76 + 10 * \log(\text{OSR}) \\ &= 6.02 * 16 + 1.76 + 10 * \log(1) \\ &= 98.08 \text{ dB (no oversampling)} \end{aligned}$$

Equation 2.6

For an eight times oversampled system:

$$\text{SNR} = 6.02 \cdot 16 + 1.76 + 10 \cdot \log(8) = 107.11 \text{ dB}$$

From this it can be said that by increasing the sampling frequency, results in a higher SNR, improving by 3 dB for every doubling of f_s , or by 0.5 bits

From the Nyquist theorem a signal must be sampled by a frequency that is at least twice the highest frequency component of a particular system. If this theory is not obeyed, reconstruction of the original signal will not be able to occur [22,23,36].

$$f_s \geq 2 \cdot f_o$$

Equation 2.7

Oversampling occurs when the signal is sampled at a higher rate, usually in integer multiples, where:

$$\text{OSR} = f_s / 2f_o$$

Equation 2.8

Oversampling is used for two main reasons:

- A simplified analogue reconstruction filter (as shown in figure *2.5) This has the benefit that the analogue filter can be designed to have a constant group delay (linear phase) over the base band, which is essential for accurate reconstruction of the original signal.
- The area of special interest to this project- the ability to reduce word lengths without loss of information [24,35].

Oversampling spreads the distortion products, over the entire oversampled spectrum. i.e. distortion products in the audible band is only a fraction of the total [25].

Figure 2.5 Oversampling with effect on frequency spectrum

For more in depth oversampling knowledge consult [3,8,35,36].

2.3.2 Noise shaping

Noise shaping (NS) is a recursive, extension to oversampling. Essentially, NS is a shifting of noise at low frequencies (i.e. audible band) to a higher un-audible frequency spectrum, using a special feedback mechanism.

There are several variations of noise shaper but in all cases, the higher the order of the shaper; the more noise is shifted out of the audible band.

The basic noise shaping consists of a delta sigma modulator that reduces the perceived re-quantisation noise level by feeding back the re-quantisation error. Note that the noise shapers shown below in figure 2.6 are directly equivalent to each other [3,9,35].

Figure 2.6 Basic NS quantisers with dither

In the frequency band of interest, 0 to 20kHz, the signal is unaffected, whereas the noise is reduced.

A filter, that models this required notation, is inserted in the feedback loop. From this two different transfer functions are produced:

One for the signal,

$$S(z) = H(z) / (1 + H(z)) \quad \text{where } z = \exp(-j\omega T), \quad j = \sqrt{-1}, \quad \omega = \text{frequency (rad/s)}, \\ T = \text{Sampling interval (s)}$$

Equation 2.9

and one for the noise,

$$N(z) = 1 / (1 + H(z)).$$

Equation 2.10

From this $H(z)$ can be calculated mathematically:

If $H(z)$ goes to infinity (at its poles), the $N(z)$ becomes zero, but the $S(z)$ remains almost the same.

To a first order approximation for low frequencies (at DC: $z=1$), $H(z)$ is found to be infinite at its poles when:

$$H(z) = (1-z)^{-1} = (z-1)/z$$

Equation 2.11

This is the transfer function of a discrete time integrator. For a first order Modulator, the transfer function is just a simple discrete delay as the $S(z)$ is:

$$S(z) = y(z)/x(z) = (1/(z-1))/(1+(1/(z-1))) = z^{-1}$$

Equation 2.12

Following this, the noise transfer function (NTF) becomes a high pass filter:

$$N(z) = y(z)/Qe(z) = 1/(1+(1/(z-1))) = (1-z^{-1})$$

Equation 2.13

Where 'Qe' represents the quantisation noise due to error

This enables the noise from the lower audible band is moved to higher frequency band (dependent on the amount of oversampling used in the first place).

The noise shaping filter $H(z)$ needs to be designed in a way, such that $(1-H(z))$ reduces noise in the audible band, shifting it to higher frequencies.

The noise power is given by $|1-1/z|$. Calculating the noise gain at a few selected frequencies (assuming $f_s = 44.1\text{kHz}$):

f (Hz)	ω (rads ⁻¹)	z	Noise gain = $ 1-1/z $
0 \Rightarrow 0kHz	0	+1	0 \Rightarrow (- ∞)
$1/(8*T) \Rightarrow$ 5.5kHz	$\pi/(4*T)$	$\exp(-j*(\pi/4))$	0.5 \Rightarrow (-3dB)
$1/(6*T) \Rightarrow$ 7.4kHz	$\pi/(3*T)$	$\exp(-j*(\pi/3))$	1 \Rightarrow (0dB)
$1/(4*T) \Rightarrow$ 11kHz	$\pi/(2*T)$	$\exp(-j*(\pi/2))$	2 \Rightarrow (+3dB)
$1/(2*T) \Rightarrow$ 22.1kHz	π/T	-1	4 \Rightarrow (+6dB)

Where, T = sampling period = $1/f_s$

Within the noise shaping system, a quantiser can be used which re-quantises the data using fewer bits. The idea is that with the amount of bits or SNR already gained from oversampling and noise shaping the signal, the word length can be reduced accordingly so that the SNR is that of the original system albeit with a reduced bit-rate.

The idea of reducing the bit-rate is perhaps the most important part in digital amplifier design as will be seen later with the limitation of power amplification.

The signal to noise ratio with oversampling and noise shaping thus becomes [35]:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{SNR} &= 10*\log(P_s/P_e) = 10*\log(1.5*2^{2n}) + 10*\log((3/\Pi^2)*\text{OSR}^2) \\ &= 6.02n + 1.76 + 30*\log(\text{OSR}) \end{aligned}$$

Equation 2.14

For an eight times oversampled system:

$$\text{SNR} = 6.02 \cdot 16 + 1.76 + 30 \cdot \log(8) = 120\text{dB}$$

This increase corresponds to a 9dB or 1.5 bit improvement in the SNR for every doubling of the OSR. (Ref. 2nd order noise shaper)

So the equivalent savings in quantiser bits relative to OSR = 1 and direct quantisation and first order noise shaping are:

OSR	Direct Quantisation	Noise Shaping
4	1	2.2
8	1.5	3.7
16	2	5.1
32	2.5	6.6
64	3	8.1

Table 2.2 First order Noise shaper bit reduction

The order of the NS converter is just as important as the noise shaping itself. The relationship of the order of the shaper to the transfer function is:

$$H(z) = (1 - z^{-1})^r, \text{ where } r = \text{shaper order}$$

Equation 2.15

This can be expressed in the frequency domain as the noise density distribution:

$$P_{\text{noise}}(f) = (2 \cdot \sin(\pi f / f_s))^r$$

Equation 2.16

The trend in reduction in quantiser bits as the order of noise shaping increases can be seen as follows:

Oversampling ratio (OSR)					
NS order	4	8	16	32	64
0	1.0	1.5	2.0	2.5	3.0
1	2.2	3.7	5.1	6.6	8.1
2	2.9	5.4	7.9	10.4	12.9
3	3.5	7.0	10.5	14.0	17.5
4	4.1	8.5	13.0	17.5	22.0
5	4.6	10.0	15.5	21.0	26.5

Table 2.3 Noise shaper bit reductions as a function of OSR and order of shaper

A further note to add on the subject of NS is the stability of the feedback mechanism, for higher orders of H(z). The stability is when the input to the quantiser becomes so large that the quantisation error becomes greater than $\pm Q/2$.

This would overload the quantiser and produce undesirable voltage instability [27].

The effect of noise shaper order upon SNR can be seen in figure 2.7. Due to the requirement of a linear phase response in the feedback filter $H(z)$, a finite impulse response (FIR) will be used, as opposed to the infinite impulse response (IIR) type.

Figure 2.7 The effect of noise shaper order on the noise level magnitude

2.3.3 Adding dither

Dither is often added prior to quantisation to eliminate distortion and noise modulation. These often audible products are the result of re-quantisation. The quantisation error creates noise that is correlated to the signal, thus introducing harmonics in the frequency spectrum. Dither reduces this by de-correlating the noise to produce noise in the form of hiss, i.e. uncorrelated white noise.

Erik Bresch points out that the effect occurs particularly when the sampling frequency and input signal are an integer multiples of one another [34].

Wannamaker[9] and Vanderkooy[10] both suggest that dither having a triangular probability density function of ± 0.5 LSB's eliminates distortion products of re-quantisation, but dither as available in SIMULINK 4 (as either white noise or a uniform random number), works just aswell.

2.4 PCM to PWM conversion

There are two main forms of PWM. These are known as Natural Pulse Width Modulation (NPWM) and Uniform Pulse Width Modulation (UPWM) [2,6,21].

Various approaches of digital PCM to PWM conversion will be looked at including:

- Ramp PWM
- Sawtooth PWM
- Direct PCM to PWM mapping

2.4.1 NPWM

The classic route for the traditional PWM amplification form is that of a natural analogue PWM amplifier (NPWM). This compares an analogue sinusoid with a ramp modulator. If the waveform is greater than the modulator, then this would result in a high pulse, falling back to zero as soon as this ceased to be true.

By Fourier analysis, the frequency spectra for this type of modulation (NPWM) is given by [2,6,7,21]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F(t) = & k + \frac{M}{2} \cos \omega t + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin m\omega t}{m\pi} \\
 & - \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{J_0(m\pi M)}{m\pi} \sin(m\omega t - 2m\pi k) \\
 & - \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=\pm 1}^{n=\pm\infty} \frac{J_n(m\pi M)}{m\pi} \sin(m\omega t + n\omega_c t - 2m\pi k - \frac{n\pi}{2})
 \end{aligned}$$

Equation 2.17

Where: k = Average amplitude of un-modulated carrier

M = Modulation index or signal amplitude

m = Index to harmonics of audio signal

n = Index to harmonics of carrier signal

ω_v = Angular frequency of input tone (rad/s)

ω_c = Angular frequency of modulator carrier (rad/s)

J_n = nth order Bessel function of the first kind

Within the spectra, there are no harmonics of the input signal. The spectrum consists of the input signal frequency, modulator with multiples and the sums and differences. This is clearly shown in the sample spectra in figure 2.8.

Figure 2.8 Sample spectra of ramp NPWM.

Due to possible fallback of the modulation products of the input signal and modulator, the carrier frequency should be at least of the order eight times that of the sampling frequency ($\sim 44.1\text{kHz}$), thus around 176.4kHz . However it is important to note that the modulator frequency should also be as low as possible [21], without being too low to affect the audible band for the lowest total harmonic distortion as can be seen in figure 2.9, provided by Intersil [29].

Figure 2.9 THD+ Noise (%) as PWM modulating frequency is varied

In the diagram the modulating frequency is varied from 150kHz to 350kHz . The lowest distortion is at 150kHz , increasing proportionally to the highest at 350kHz . Note that the graph is an analogue D-class amplifier.

2.4.2 Ramp UPWM

Taking the theory from the analogue system, the spectra of a uniformly sampled PWM system is examined [2,6,21], to see how it effects the PWM resulting signal.

For ramp UPWM the Fourier components are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 F(t) = & k - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{J_n\left(\frac{n\pi M\omega_v}{\omega_c}\right)}{\frac{n\pi\omega_v}{\omega_c}} \sin\left(m\omega_c t - \frac{2n\pi k\omega_v}{\omega_c} - \frac{n\pi}{2}\right) \\
 & + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1 - J_0(m\pi M)}{m\pi} \sin m\omega_c t \\
 & - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=\pm 1}^{\pm\infty} \frac{J_n\left[\frac{(m\omega_c + n\omega_v)\pi M}{\omega_c}\right]}{(m\omega_c + n\omega_v)\frac{\pi}{\omega_c}} \sin\left((m\omega_c + n\omega_v)\left(t - \frac{2\pi k}{\omega_c}\right) - \frac{n\pi}{2}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Equation 2.18

On analysis of the above equation, the presence of distortion terms can be seen as harmonics of the input signal. The amplitude of the harmonics increase with both modulation frequency and index. Furthermore, like the analogue system, the spectrum contains the carrier with multiples and the sums and differences of the input signal and its multiples.

A sample ramp UPWM spectrum is shown in figure 2.10.

Figure 2.10 Sample spectra of ramp UPWM

The pulse width in PWM is directly proportional to the height of the quantised signal. This is shown in a sample analysis of the uniformly sampled and quantised input signal, modulated against a ramp carrier to produce UPWM.

Figure 2.11 Ramp UPWM formation

2.4.3 Sawtooth UPWM

Again, this form of PWM is looked at from an analytical perspective. This is characterised by the following decomposition by Fourier analysis:

$$F(t) = k + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2J_n\left(\frac{M\pi n\omega}{2\omega}\right)}{\pi n \frac{\omega}{\omega}} \sin\left(n\left(1 - \frac{\omega}{\omega}\right)\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \cos\left(n\omega t - \pi n \frac{\omega}{\omega}\right) + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} \frac{2J_n\left(\frac{M\pi n\omega}{2\omega}\right)}{\pi\left(m+n\frac{\omega}{\omega}\right)} \sin\left(\left(m+n\left(1 - \frac{\omega}{\omega}\right)\right)\frac{\pi}{2}\right) \cos\left(n\omega t + m\omega t - \pi n \frac{\omega}{\omega}\right)$$

Equation 2.19

Similarly to the ramp UPWM, modulation products of the carrier and input signal are present, with harmonic content in the audible region. This form of PWM has been well documented in the past by several researchers [2,6,21] and has been noted that the base band harmonics drop off faster for sawtooth UPWM than ramp UPWM. This is shown graphically in the form of figure 2.12.

Figure 2.12 Sample spectra of sawtooth UPWM

The uniformly sampled timing diagrams for sawtooth UPWM are shown in the below figure 2.13.

Figure 2.13 Sawtooth UPWM formation

2.4.4 Direct PCM to PWM mapping

The last type of digital conversion that will be looked at is possibly the most desirable of all, as it involves directly converting the PCM signal to PWM. This direct mapping contains no harmonics, as it does not have an error associated with the carrier/modulator. Oversampling and noise shaping could be used to reduce the bit rate in order to allow amplification by MOSFET technology. i.e. Highest operational frequency of around 100 to 150MHz. There would no modulation losses as seen previously and linearisation would not be required. The graphical concept of the direct mapping of PWM from PCM is illustrated in figure 2.14.

where 1.0 represents $(2^{16})-1$ levels

Figure 2.14 Direct UPWM formation

2.5 Linearisation of the PCM

A conversion of uniformly sampled PCM data to PWM data using a sawtooth/ramp waveform results in a high harmonic content in the audio band, as seen previously. The PCM data must be somehow pre-distorted before being converted to PWM, so that the inherent non-linearities are compensated.

The Linearisation of PWM is not a new concept. Several researchers have developed linearisers in the past [1,2,4,5,6,21,34].

To visualise the problem; when an analogue waveform is modulated using the PWM mechanism, the resultant output is free from harmonics in the base band. The difference between analogue and digital form is that the digital is made up of samples, rather than being of a continuous nature and would thus result in different spectra, as seen previously.

This problem can be rectified by adding a pre-distortion signal processing linearisation algorithm or ‘cross point deriver’ [4]. This aims to digitally emulate the harmonic distortion free analogue form. Linearisation will be discussed in depth in the implementation chapter.

2.6 D-class amplification

Due to the design difficulty and possible high distortion, relatively little research activity has been directed towards the more efficient class-D switching amplifiers based on PWM. Class-D amplifiers are unique in that the efficiency approaches 100% independent of the operation power level:

$$\text{Efficiency} = P_l/P_{dc}$$

Equation 2.20

Where P_l = AC load power output (W)

P_{dc} = DC input power (W)

The high efficiency is due to the active output devices (MOSFETs), which are either fully conducting or are fully non-conducting at any given moment in time. This has been described in the literature [7,14,18,19].

In theory there is no power-dissipating element in the power amplifier section except for the loudspeaker itself. This is however, assuming that the low pass filter networks are perfect inductors and capacitors, with no resistance.

The power stage of a class-D amplifier uses high power MOSFET's in either half or h-bridge configuration, to increase the amplitude of the PWM.

The power amplifier can be seen as a high power DC voltage source and a switch which is controlled by the low power PWM signal.

2.6.1 Half Bridge D-class power stage operation

The modulated PWM drives one MOSFET into saturation, putting the other into its off position.

The PWM output causes the switches to change state as fast as possible, given the operating frequency of the switch. Fast switching limits the time that the switches spend in the linear operating region, thereby increasing the efficiency and reducing heat generation.

The basic design of the half bridge is shown in figure 2.15.

Figure 2.15 Half Bridge D-class amplifier

2.6.2 Full/H-Bridge D-class power stage operation

The full bridge develops a peak-to-peak load voltage equal to double the supply. The full bridge uses only one voltage supply. The four MOSFET's always turn on and off in pairs. For the load current to flow into the H-bridge, two switches must be on simultaneously. The inverter provides the switching control so that when S1 and S4 are on, S2 and S3 are off and vice versa. AOUT and BOUT are current sensing terminals and are available for current feedback control.

The basic configuration of the H/full Bridge is illustrated in figure 2.16.

Figure 2.16 Full Bridge/H D-class amplifier

When a load is applied between AOUT and BOUT, current flows from V_s to ground in one of two routes:

V_s to S1 to the load connected between AOUT and BOUT, to S4 and then to ground or, V_s to S3, to the load, to S2 and finally to ground.

The doubling of the voltage output results in the need for a low pass filter on each output. To do this using traditional linear class A/A.B, two amplifiers must be used in a bridge configuration.

The name H-bridge refers to the way that the circuit is often drawn and is more often than not referred to as this rather than a full bridge. The H-bridge avoids a DC-offset across the load in the quiescent operating point [40].

2.6.3 Analogue and Digital D-class amplifier feedback

Often, feedback techniques are used to linearise and maintain tight, consistent control of amplifier gain and frequency response. A high gain feedback loop will enhance transient response and minimise distortion over an audible frequency range [33]. An analogue D-class amplifier diagram is shown in figure 2.17.

Figure 2.17 Analogue D-class amplifier structure

More crucially, the digital D-class amplifier cannot easily include a feedback loop, due to the many delays introduced by using a possible analogue to digital converter (ADC). A feedback network would help solve the problems associated with distortion from a non-ideal power MOSFET and the stabilisation of the H-bridge itself [40]. The stabilisation is especially important as a D-class amplifier has a 0dB power supply rejection ratio [21].

The design shall, however progress without using feedback in an open loop structure.

2.6.4 MOSFET Selection

The MOSFET's used within the D-class amplifier output stage have losses and voltages associated with them, just like any other device [19,20,33].

The peak voltage and current determine the required ratings that the MOSFET must be able to sustain, where:

$$V_{pk} = \sqrt{(2 * P_{out} * Z_{load})}$$

Equation 2.21

$$I_{pk} = V_{pk} / Z_{load}$$

Equation 2.22

E.g. if $P_{out} = 100w$ into an 8Ω loudspeaker

$$V_{pk} = \sqrt{(2 * 100 * 8)} = 40V$$

$$I_{pk} = 40 / 8 = 5A$$

This means that the MOSFET's must have a breakdown voltage $B_{VDSS} \geq 50V$ for compliance and a current rating $I_D \geq 5A$.

For improved amplifier efficiency, a MOSFET with a low drain to source resistance ($R_{DS(on)}$) must be chosen.

i.e. a MOSFET with an $R_{DS_{ON}}$ 180m Ω would reduce the efficiency by:

$$\mu = (100 \cdot 2 \cdot R_{DS_{ON}}) / Z_{load} = (100 \cdot 2 \cdot 0.18) / 8 = 4.5\%$$

Equation 2.23

i.e. A maximum efficiency of 95.5% is now only available, dependent upon the losses of the rest of the system.

The highest efficiency occurs when:

$R_{DS_{ON}}$, filter resistances, stray resistances $\gg Z_{load}$

Including switching losses, a new model for the efficiency can be developed [33], where:

$$\eta = \frac{\frac{R_{LOAD}}{(2 \cdot r_{DSON} + R_{LOAD} + R_X)}}{1 + f_{PWM} \cdot \left[\frac{16 \cdot V_{BUS}}{\pi^2 \cdot I_{RATE} \cdot (2 \cdot r_{DSON} + R_{LOAD} + R_X)} \dots + 2 \cdot I_{RATE} \cdot \frac{t_{RR}^2}{V_{BUS}} \cdot (2 \cdot r_{DSON} + R_{LOAD} + R_X) \right]}$$

Equation 2.24

2.7 Demodulation

Class-D amplifiers differ from their linear counterparts in that, an output filter is required to remove the high frequency components of the PWM signal.

The low pass filtered PWM signal would ideally filter out all of the high frequency components, leaving only the original input signal behind, hence the name demodulation.

The requirement of the low pass filtering does not need to be too stringent [33] and a 25kHz to 30kHz cut-off of order 2 to 4 such suffice [19]. This is due to the modulator being four times the sampling frequency

For basic filter design, there are several variations with slightly different characteristics.

The Butterworth filter has a frequency response characteristic, which is maximally flat in the pass band. The Chebyshev filter exhibits slightly sharper attenuation with frequency than the Butterworth, but suffers from ripple in the pass band.

The Bessel filter is optimised to produce a maximally flat delay in the pass band and the step response has virtually no overshoot but the roll-off is somewhat short of the others.

2.8 Test and Measurement

The specifications that determine an amplifier's audio performance are subject to much debate. As an engineer, the performance of a digital amplifier must be judged against the following criteria [29,30].

2.8.1 Signal to noise ratio (SNR)

The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) for an amplifier is the ratio between the maximum output signal and the noise level at zero output [39]. The measurement bandwidth is usually 20 Hz to 20 kHz, with or without A-weighting [30].

$$\text{SNR} = V(\text{rms,max}) / V(\text{rms,noise})$$

Equation 2.25

Figure 2.18 Signal to Noise ratio

2.8.2 Total Harmonic Distortion + Noise (THD + N)

The total harmonic distortion plus noise is directly related to the linearity of a system. It includes the harmonic components, as well as quantisation and intermodulation distortion.

The total harmonic distortion is the sum of all of the harmonics, but in practice is limited seven harmonic terms [29]. Figure 2.19 shows a typical harmonic distortion spectrum. As already described, a switching amplifier has some out-of-band components. This means that the measurement of the THD+N should be strictly limited to the audible region, where:

$$\text{THD+N} = \frac{\text{Fundamental RMS signal voltage value}}{\text{harmonics}_{(\text{RMS})} + \text{noise}}$$

Equation 2.26

Alternatively, more specifically, the THD is given by:

$$V_{THD} = \sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^N \left(\frac{V_n}{V_1}\right)^2}$$

where

n = Integer harmonic number

V_{THD} = Total harmonic voltage distortion factor

V_n = Harmonic voltage

V_1 = Fundamental voltage

Equation 2.27

Figure 2.19 Harmonic distortion spectrum

2.8.3 Dynamic Range

The EIAJ standard measurement for dynamic range is done by reading THD+N at an input amplitude of -60dB . The result will give the range between full output (0 dB) and the noise floor of the amplifier. To provide a valid result, the measurement bandwidth must be in the audible region ($20\text{ Hz}-20\text{ kHz}$).

E.g.

If the measurement with a -60 dB input signal level gives a THD+N of 53 dB , the dynamic range of the amplifier is $(53 + 60)\text{ dB} = 113\text{ dB}$.

2.8.4 Channel separation

Channel separation is defined as the ratio of the signal level on one channel while the opposite channel is held at idle level. i.e. this is a measure of crosstalk between adjacent channels. It can be measured by evaluating distortion on the idle channel when the opposite channel has data present.

2.8.5 Efficiency

Relative to class A and A/B, class D amplifiers offer a vast improvement in efficiency [7,14,19].

The efficiency of an digital amplifier is given by:

$$\eta = 100 * \frac{V_{(rms,ch1)} * I_{(rms,ch1)} + V_{(rms,ch1)} * I_{(rms,ch1)}}{V_{(dc,input)} * I_{(dc,input)}}$$

Equation 2.28

3. IMPLEMENTATION

3.1 Chapter overview

The modelling of the system utilises MATLAB [37,38] and MATLAB-SIMULINK, Mentor Graphics and PSPICE. Several parts of the digital amplifier concept have been thoroughly explored. A full MATLAB-SIMULINK model has been developed to give an evaluation of a digital amplifier.

It was found to be extremely difficult to model a non-linear system such as a MOSFET in the D-class power stage, so a perfect switch was assumed for example.

Likewise, Mentor Graphics and PSPICE are very powerful tools in their own right, but are limited, especially in the time available, in simulating complex digital structures.

However, several simulations were carried out to show direct PCM to PWM mapping, the principle of the PWM concept using an analogue signal and a H-bridge D class amplifier with demodulation.

Finally, another MATLAB program was developed to show the techniques involved in the realisation of a solution. This includes a simple GUI, which allows you to enter the input signal frequency, type and frequency of sawtooth, oversampling ratio, demodulating frequency and shows various low pass filter topologies.

It will be up to future research to fine tune a full hardware solution and this shall be discussed in the end of this chapter and in the further work section in chapter 7.

3.2 Hardware Interfacing

Having tested the CD output it was found that the required PCM bi-phase TTL output wasn't as expected. On exploration of the problem, a circuit was developed to convert the digital output into the correct format. This circuit is shown in figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1 - Schematic of S/PDIF to bi-phase TTL

Having done this, it was found that a phase locked loop would be required, in order to extract the data and clock. It seemed reasonable to research the market place for already available solutions to the problem. Contact was made with Crystal Semiconductors in America and their PR manager sponsored the project by sending two CDB8415A SPDIF [31] interface boards and ten-silicon receiver CS8415A [32] chips. The SPDIF interface board was supplied with a Windows 98 GUI to allow easy selection and evaluation of the various software modes.

A Marantz CD-63 CD player was used to supply the board with an SPDIF input. The test CD, (mentioned later on in this chapter) developed using MATLAB provided the EIA-560 [28] test frequencies to allow testing of the CD player and SPDIF interface board.

The CDB8415A allows connection to seven coaxial SPDIF sources and one optical TOSLINK.

The board allows access to the entire block format of a PCM stream, but as an overview, the output pins OLRCK and SDOUT provided the necessary sampling frequency clock(f_s) and serial data out. RCBL indicates the start of a block (CS).

The board and CD player were tested using a 1kHz sine wave in both the time and frequency domains using a Gould 500 digital storage scope (200MHz bandwidth) and an Anritsu MS2601 spectrum analyser. Intermodulation tests were carried out using the EIA-560 standards of 11kHz and 12kHz [28]. The CDB8415A was tested in software mode only, as this offers the maximum versatility.

A schematic was designed to interface with the CDB8415A, allowing detection of the three different preambles (see chapter 2.1). On detection, the circuit shifts the data only through to a custom designed PCM to PWM converter. (see appendix B, figure 10.2)

3.3 Oversampling and Dithered Noise Shaping Quantisers

3.3.1 Oversampling

Oversampling is nothing more other than increasing the ratio of the sampling frequency by an integer value.

For implementation interpolation is used, whereby calculation of new samples is done in between those already created at 44.1kHz. The oversampling process requires initially the insertion of (R_n-1) zero samples per Nyquist interval followed by a low pass filter to band limit the signal to the $0.5 \cdot f_s$. The process of low pass filtering effectively calculates the new sample values by eliminating the aliased products of zero insertion to complete the realisation of interpolation. The effect of zeros interleaving and oversampling on a signal is shown below in figure 3.2)

Figure 3.2 The effect of zeros interleaving and oversampling on a signal

The notation of oversampling in smaller steps, rather than in a large step is noted to produce a more efficient interpolation mechanism, as the filter orders can be relaxed. The SIMULINK model for this is shown in figure 3.3.

An investigation into different interpolation mechanisms is looked at using MATLAB and the SIMULINK system. This includes using Lagrange, linear and standard interpolation. This is extended by using Sinc interpolation which is based upon the idea that a sine wave can be made up of an infinite amount of scaled and time shifted sinc functions for the benefit of reconstruction.

Figure 3.3 Separation of FIR interpolators for optimization

The interpolation seen above is oversampling the signal by a factor of eight, so the new effective sampling frequency is 352800Hz.

3.3.2 Noise Shaping

There are problems associated with the design of noise shapers. Due to the non-linear characteristics of quantisation, higher order shapers often lead to instability, oscillating out of control. The filter is therefore often limited to fifth order as shown by [1,3,8,26,35].

From theory it can be shown that $1-H(z)$ must be minimum phase in order to preserve the capacity of the channel [9,26].

The theory has already been previously discussed so the discussion of the development of the noise shapers shall proceed.

Aswell as noise shaping the frequency spectrum by shifting the noise out of the audio band, the system also proceeds in reducing the word length by using re-quantisation. MATLAB SIMULINK was used to produce simulations of the different noise shapers to find out how they would effect the system in its entirety. The Oppenheim [35] or standard noise shaper is shown in SIMULINK form in figure 3.4. Dither was added in the form of a random number generator at a voltage of $\pm 0.5/256$, which is $\frac{1}{2}$ LSB as the quantiser, re-quantises the data to eight bits in order to realise a practical solution.

Figure 3.4 A Standard fifth order Noise shaper

Further to this, the work carried out on filter Noise Transfer Functions (NTF) by Goldberg and Sandler [2] was utilised; in order to realise an optimised NTF response for the feedback filter, $H(z)$. He proposed that while the standard NTF's developed in the past have had optimal base band performance, they also tend to have high noise power gain at high frequencies. In practice, the increased high frequency noise power from the noise shaping is large enough to cause undesirable effects after modulation, resulting in a loss in the base band SNR at the output of the pulse width modulator.

The co-efficients of the fifth order filter by numerical optimisation procedure are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 C[0] &= -1.0 \\
 C[1] &= 2.976059 \\
 C[2] &= -2.501200 \\
 C[3] &= -0.6206618 \\
 C[4] &= 1.812384 \\
 C[5] &= -0.6703392
 \end{aligned}$$

This is seen graphically in figure 3.5. It was implemented in MATLAB and in SIMULINK using the filter realisation wizard.

Figure 3.5 Goldberg and Sandler proposed optimised NTF response.

Another type of noise shaper utilises discrete integrators in order to noise shape the signal. This topology was described by Hawksford [4]. It provides open loop gain, peaking at high frequencies, reducing to 0dB in the audible band. Similarly to the standard topology; as the order of the shaper increases so does the likelihood of instability. The fifth order shaper is shown in figure 3.6.

Figure 3.6 Hawksford proposed fifth order Noise shaper

With either of the proposed noise shapers, the re-quantised signal is eight bits. This, in addition to the 8x oversampling gives an effective new bit rate of:

$$f_{\text{Sover}} * 2^n = 352800 * 2^8 \approx 90.3\text{MHz}$$

Equation 3.1

This allows a practical implementation of the D-class power stage to be undertaken. It will be shown that the noise shapers will effectively give a 16-bit resolution even though the word length has been reduced to eight bits.

3.4 PCM to PWM conversion

The conversion from PCM to PWM data was implemented in MATLAB, followed by SIMULINK. The use of SIMULINK was required to realise the noise shapers and linearisers in a pseudo real time environment.

The basic conversion processes of PWM are shown in figures 3.7 and figures 3.8 respectively.

Figure 3.7 Model of a Ramp Uniform Pulse Width Modulator

Figure 3.8 Model of a Sawtooth Uniform Pulse Width Modulator

This, as briefly mentioned beforehand equates to the equation:

$$\text{PWM} = \text{Qsignal} > \text{Modulator}$$

Equation 3.2

Qsignal = Quantised PCM signal

Modulator = Ramp or Sawtooth generator

The generation of the Ramp and Sawtooth is done at a frequency of 352800Hz to match the oversampled frequency. The subsystems for each are shown below.

Figure 3.9 Ramp UPWM subsystem

Figure 3.10 Sawtooth UPWM subsystem

A schematic was designed in Mentor Graphics (see appendix C, figure 10.2) to show the application of direct PCM to PWM mapping. The block diagram format of this schematic is shown in figure 3.11.

Figure 3.11 System block diagram of direct PCM to UPWM conversion

The PCM input signal is assumed to be serial. Using:

$$\text{Clk1} = 44.1\text{e3} * 16$$

$$\text{Clk2} = 44.1\text{e3} * (2^{16} - 1)$$

The sync pulse resets the system every 44.1kHz, setting the SR flip-flop. At the same time the storage register clocks the data through to be compared with the counter. This allows a mapping of the 16-bit PCM word, into an equivalent PWM signal.

E.g. 1111111111111111 \Rightarrow pulse width high for $1/44.1\text{e3}$

0000000000000000 \Rightarrow pulse width low for $1/44.1\text{e3}$

1010101010101010 \Rightarrow pulse width high for $1/(65535 * 44.1\text{e3})$, then low for the

remaining time.

However, for a practical system, this would not be possible as the bit rate would be too high for current MOSFET technology.

For the system proposed, throughout the paper, the counters and comparators would be re-placed with eight bit versions, due to the re-quantised noise shapers.

The clocks would also change to:

$$\text{Clk1} = 44.1\text{e3} * 8$$

$$\text{Clk2} = 44.1\text{e3} * (2^8 - 1)$$

This would then be compliant with current MOSFET standards. This principle was then taken to another level, by implementing the block frame structure of the SPDIF standard. This is shown in the appendix C, figure 10.5 and 10.6.

3.5 Linearisation of the PCM

3.5.1 Ramp UPWM linearisation

As mentioned previously, the PCM data needs to be pre-distorted, mimicking a continuous form. The linearisation for Ramp UPWM was first perceived by Goldberg and Sandler [2]. They named the process ‘pseudo-natural PWM’. The basic idea of this notation is considered below in figure 3.12 [21]:

Figure 3.12 – PNPWM Concept

For successful cross point derivation, a continuous reconstruction of the analogue signal is required. To satisfy theory a sine wave can be made up of an infinite amount of scaled

and shifted sinc functions [36]. To an approximation, this would involve all PCM samples before and after one another using an n th order polynomial. A numerical approximation such as Newton Raphson could be utilised or perhaps indeed Lagrange polynomials as shown in figure 3.13.

(a) No correction

(b) 1 point correction

(c) 2 point correction

Figure 3.13 Sample waveform showing use of Lagrange Polynomials to aid reconstruction

An important note to add is that the lineariser must precede any noise shaping mechanism, as attempting to noise shape prior to computing the cross point times will represent extra complexity, due to the extra high frequency noise components.

Likewise, the Newton Raphson algorithm allows highly accurate cross point derivation and has been researched by [2,34].

The basic process is illustrated below in figure 3.14 for a third order polynomial approximation. In the diagram $t(t)$ is the ramp modulator and $x(t)$ is the ‘underlying’ analogue signal of which is sampled at uniform instants in time.

Figure 3.14 PNPWM Newton Raphson approximation, third order polynomial

The procedure for this is as follows [2]:

- Compute 3rd order Newton co-efficients by substitution
- Use Newton Raphson method to find the cross point in time, where:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{test}(n+1) &= \text{test}(n) + f(\text{test}(n)) / f'(\text{test}(n)) \\ &= \text{test}(n) - \frac{(c_3 * t^{3 \text{ est}(n)} + c_2 * t^{3 \text{ est}(n)} + c_1 * t^{3 \text{ est}(n)} + c_0)}{(3 * c_3 * t^{3 \text{ est}(n)} + 2 * c_2 * t^{3 \text{ est}(n)} + c_1)} \end{aligned}$$

Equation 3.3

- Store and Repeat procedure

where Cx = Co-efficients

t_{est} = true cross point time estimate

The PNPWM method allows the correction of harmonic distortion in the audio band by mimicking the idea of a continuous waveform. The algorithm developed is only suitable for a ramp modulator.

3.5.3 Sawtooth UPWM linearisation

For correcting the harmonic distortion problems in the audio band for a sawtooth modulator, a different algorithm needs to be developed.

Hawksford [4,5] proposed a solution using a dynamic filter idea consisting of an FIR filter structure.

The filter structure can be observed below in figure 3.15. The co-efficients are not constant as they are uniquely associated with each sample value. i.e. as the samples are shifted through the FIR filter, the co-efficients are also shifted through the individual co-efficient sets. The FIR filter is chosen due to its linear phase attributes.

To understand this principle, recall that the NPWM signal is free from harmonics and that a PCM signal in-itself is also harmonic free. It is only when the PCM signal is converted to PWM that the harmonics occur.

A PCM system consists of constant widths with varying level, whereby its transfer function remains the same but with amplitude scaling. Unfortunately a PWM's transfer function by Fourier analysis varies both in amplitude and frequency scaling and therefore needs to be compensated for so that the Fourier transform characteristic is constant in the base band and like PCM simply amplitude scaled.

Figure 3.15 Five co-efficient fourth order FIR filter structure

The filter is designed in order to change accordingly, whereby the impulse response of the FIR correction filter is obtained from the inverse Fourier transform of the PWM's spectrum.

The transfer function of the filter is:

$$TF_F(f) = c_0 + 2*c_1*\cos(2*\Pi*(f/f_{NY})) + 2*c_2*\cos(4*\Pi*(f/f_{NY}))$$

Where $c_0 + 2*c_1 + 2*c_2$ are the various co-efficients equal to one for unity (dc)

f = applied frequency (Hz)

f_{NY} = Nyquist frequency (Hz)

The frequency spectrum of the PWM samples to be corrected utilises a sinc function, where:

$$TF_{\text{PWM}} = \text{sinc}(y(n) \cdot T_c \cdot f)$$

$y(n)$ = PWM sample to be sampled (0 to 1, with 1 representing 1 maximum pulse width)_

T_c = Pulse width (s)

f = applied frequency (Hz)

However as Hawksford [4,5] points out, for this method to be 100% accurate, an infinite amount of co-efficients would be required, thus an approximation is made. The magnitude response corresponds to a 50% duty cycle PWM pulse, i.e. PWM pulse length of $0.5 \cdot T_c$.

$\Rightarrow \text{sinc}(0.5 \cdot T_c \cdot f)$ for 0 to 20kHz

Therefore chose a modulation index of 0.5.

A final note to add regarding the design of the filter is that it requires oversampling of at least a factor of four for good results [34].

For further information regarding the design of the dynamic filter method, see appendix D.

3.6 D-class amplification

It has been found that the implementation of a digital amplifier is limited to the power amplification stage. Due to MOSFET technology having operational frequencies up to 100-150MHz, the amount of oversampling and length of PCM word will have to be limited accordingly.

For 16-bit resolution digital amplifier with a CD player source, the operational frequency would have to be:

$$(2^n - 1) \cdot f_s = 2^{16} \cdot 44.1 \text{e}3 \approx 2.9 \text{GHz}$$

Obviously, this is not actually possible with current MOSFET technology, which is limited to about 100 to 150MHz [20].

This means that the pulse widths generated would need to be defined to an accuracy of 0.346ns (~2.9GHz). This is closer to ECL, which unfortunately cannot be used for D-class amplification.

This is immediately imposing practical limitations on the digital amplifier. For the current MOSFET technology available, the limitation in resolution is around 11 bits. A compromise of this amplitude is un-acceptable in the analogue world, let alone the digital.

Browsing table 2.3 in the previous chapter, the concept of oversampling and noise shaping allows a solution to be realised.

A decision was made to use an eight times oversampled, fifth order noise shaping eight-bit quantiser.

This reduces the bit rate to a realistic 90.3MHz.

A simple version of the D-class amplifier was modelled using SIMULINK, which as already mentioned assumes linear switching. The ideal switches are powered by a modelled DC voltage supply, which can be changed in order to apply different amounts of gain. The subsystem is shown in figure 3.16.

Figure 3.16 Class-D amplifier model

The H-bridge schematic was designed using Mentor Graphics and has a 60 volt supply powering MTD3055VL MOSFET's by ON semiconductors. This satisfies all requirements of efficiency, power and switching frequency.

i.e.

$R_{DS_{ON}} = 180\text{m}\Omega$

$R_{load} = 8\Omega$

$F_{pwm} = 8 * 44.1\text{e}3 = 352800\text{Hz}$

$T_{rr} = <10\text{ ns} \Rightarrow 100\text{MHz}$ maximum switching frequency

$B_{VDSS} = 50\text{V}$

$I_D = 12\text{A}$

i.e. a MOSFET with an $R_{DS_{ON}} = 180\text{m}\Omega$ would reduce the efficiency by:

$$\mu = (100 * 2 * R_{DS_{ON}}) / Z_{load} = (100 * 2 * 0.18) / 8 = 4.5\%$$

$$\therefore \text{efficiency} = 95.5\%$$

The total power dissipation @25° is 48W

3.7 Demodulation

The low pass LC filter was tested at various cut-off frequencies with different types of filter structures in MATLAB, including Butterworth, Chebyshev and Elliptic(Cauer) designs. The designs were to meet the following specification, wherever appropriate:

Order = 4

Pass band cutoff frequency = 25kHz

Pass band variation = 0.001dB

Stop band Attenuation = -60dB

This is shown in the following three figures.

Figure 3.17 Butterworth 4th order low pass filter frequency response

Figure 3.18 Chebyshev 4th order low pass filter frequency response

Figure 3.19 Elliptic(Cauer) fourth order low pass filter frequency response

The variations in response were very similar. The elliptic design had the maximum roll-off at 100kHz (>-50dB from reference). However, it also had the worst roll-off from the pass band to 40kHz.

In the SIMULINK design, a fourth order butterworth filter was used with a pass band edge frequency of 25kHz.

For ease of design, a second order butterworth filter with a pass band edge frequency of 30kHz was designed to demodulate the PWM, just to illustrate the principle.

The transfer function of a second order butterworth filter is:

$$H(s) = 1/(s^2 + \sqrt{2}s + 1)$$

Equation 3.4

Figure 3.20 Second order low pass butterworth filter

The AOUT and BOUT names are used in the SIMULINK system, just to differentiate the two outputs exiting the H-bridge.

In order to analyse the filter design, a half circuit approach is taken, where C_f is split into two series capacitors of equal value and the speaker impedance is effectively halved. The inductor and capacitor are converted to the frequency domain, using Laplace:

$$L_p = L_p * s$$

$$2C_f = 2 / (C_f * s)$$

Ignoring C_1 and C_2 the following figure is created:

Figure 3.21 Half circuit analysis

Using frequency domain representations of the inductance and capacitance:

$$L \Rightarrow Ls$$

$$C \Rightarrow 1/Cs$$

The transfer function, V_{in}/V_{out} can be solved:

$$\frac{V_{out}(s)}{V_{in}(s)} = H_F(s) = \frac{Z_T}{L_P s + Z_T}$$

$$Z_T = 2C_f \parallel \frac{R_L}{2}$$

Equation 3.4

∴

$$H_F(s) = \frac{R_L/2}{(L_P \cdot 2C_f \cdot R_L/2) \cdot s^2 + L_P \cdot s + R_L/2}$$

Equation 3.5

Equating H(s) and H_F(s) ⇒

$$L_P = \frac{\sqrt{2} \cdot R_L}{2\omega_o}$$

Equation 3.6

$$C_f = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2 \cdot R_L/2 \cdot \omega_o}$$

Equation 3.7

Where $\omega_o = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot f$

Therefore, $L_P = 30 \mu\text{H}$ and $C_f = 0.47 \mu\text{F}$ for the nearest available values.

Component values for C1 and C2 are used to provide an AC ground path and are chosen to be 20% of the value of C_f, C_f being 1nF [19].

3.8 Complete System

A summary of the digital open loop amplifier system proposed in this project is shown in figure 3.19

Figure 3.22 Proposed Digital Amplifier Block Diagram

The S/PDIF interface for the CD player was implemented using a Crystal Semiconductors CDB8415A interface board. The linearisation, oversampling and noise shaping have been developed using MATLAB and SIMULINK. The PCM to PWM conversion was implemented in MATLAB, SIMULINK and Mentor Graphics. The Block/frame sequence of the S/PDIF standard was utilised in a Mentor Graphics schematic, in addition to the PCM to PWM conversion. The D-class amplifier and the demodulator were produced in SIMULINK and Mentor Graphics.

The Mentor Graphics and PSPICE schematics are shown in the appendices. The SIMULINK digital amplifier design is shown in figure 3.20.

Figure 3.23 Complete SIMULINK schematic of a digital amplifier.

3.9 Proposed System

Had time been permitting, the proposed system would have consisted of the following components, as shown in figure 3.20.

Figure 3.24 Proposed Digital Amplifier Practical Solution

The Marantz CD player, when playing a CD would send the CDB8415A data in a SPDIF format. The CDN8415A would in turn send the following signals to the XILINX XC-2V40 FPGA:

OLRCK – Sub-frame clock = $f_s = 44.1\text{kHz}$

SDOUT = Serial Data

RCBL = Received Channel Status Block ~Start of data block

The XILINX XC2V40 FPGA can work up to 400MHz and allows up to 40,000 gates, which is above and beyond the requirement.

The FPGA would contain the developed schematic, which would extract the 16-bit data for the left and right channel. As the left channel occurs first, this would be delayed by a subframe (see chapter 2.1), which is $1/(44.1\text{e}3*2)$. This is done so that the left and right channel data are sent at the same time.

The left and right data are sent to the Texas Instruments TMS320C6701. The DSP chipset can be programmed in 'C' language and would be used for the implementation of any oversampling, linearisation and noise shaping that might be used. The TMS320C6701 can be used up to 167MHz and has 1M-bit of on board S-RAM.

The DSP board would send back the processed signal in 8-bit data form, for each of the channels. The FPGA2 would contain the three proposed PCM to PWM conversion processes to allow evaluation of each.

The Harris HIP4080AEVAL H-Bridge would amplify the PWM signal. However, having looked at the distortion values for the board, they are not in the same league as class 'A' amplifier specifications, so a custom design may have to be designed, using the basic design already designed in MENTOR GRAPHICS.

Following this, the amplified PWM is demodulated using a fourth order, 25kHz pass band edge frequency and the resulting sinusoid is applied to the loudspeaker.

3.10 Test and Measurement

A MATLAB program was developed to produce stereo frequencies across the entire frequency range in accordance to the EIA 560 audio systems committee standards [28]. Intermodulation tones were also produced to test for intermodulation distortion. The MATLAB program produced .wav files, which were subsequently put onto a writeable CD. The CD was used for the testing of the Crystal Semiconductors CDB8415A interface evaluation board and the CD player itself. For reference purposes, a single tone of 1kHz was tested, along with 11kHz and 12kHz for the intermodulation testing. Various tests were completed using both the time and frequency domain. See appendix A for more details.

All MATLAB SIMULINK designs were simulated over a time period of 0.1 seconds in order to get an FFT window size of at least 4096 for each component.

Example (worst case)

For a sampling rate of 44.1kHz, this represents a sample period of $1/44.1e3$. For 0.1 seconds this gives:

$$0.1/(1/44.1e3) = 4410 \text{ samples,} \quad \text{i.e. greater than 4096}$$

For oversampled systems, this will yield a window size of 'n' times 4410, 'n' being the ratio of oversampling. However, MATLAB is limited to storing 10,000 samples.

In each case a rectangular hanning window of length(no. of samples) was used for spectral analysis.

A 6kHz 90% full-scale frequency ($\pm 0.45V$) was chosen for the single frequency test. As Bresch points out [8,40], this particular frequency represents the worst-case scenario for a 12kHz second order harmonic and an 18kHz third order harmonic component. For the intermodulation tests, the recommended CCIF IM, EIA 560 standards [28] were used. These standards are used in industry for CD player testing. These frequencies are required to be at 45% full scale at 11kHz and 12kHz respectively.

A problem with simulating the entire system is the computational complexity. For a 400MHz, 128MB equipped PC a simulation lasting 0.1 seconds will take around 5 hours to complete.

The Mentor Graphics and PSPICE schematics were simulated for enough time to illustrate the working design.

4. RESULTS

Chapter overview

The results from testing the CD player and Crystal Semiconductors CDB8415A are presented. A comparison of different interpolators are shown to give the reader an idea of the effectiveness of the different types, available in MATLAB.

The results from the digital amplifier SIMULINK model are shown to give an overview of the processes involved.

Finally, the results from the PCM to PWM Mentor Graphics designs and the PSPICE ramp modulated PWM is shown.

4.1 CD player and CDB8415A testing

Various tests were carried out on the Marantz CD-63 CD player, with and without the developed S/PDIF to TTL conversion and the Crystal Semiconductors CDB8415A interface connected.

This was done to help understand the S/PDIF interface and its associated components.

Note that the S/PDIF to TTL conversion relates to figure 3.1. and that the signals:

OLRCK = Reference clock signal, $f_s=44.1\text{kHz}$

SDOUT = Serial data out

Figure 4.1 1kHz left and right channel analogue out (super-imposed), time domain

Figure 4.2 11kHz and 12kHz left and right channel analogue out (super-imposed), time domain

Figure 4.3 No signal, digital out, time domain

Figure 4.4 1kHz signal, digital out, time domain

Figure 4.5 No signal, digital out, developed TTL circuit super-imposed, time domain

Figure 4.6 OLRCK, $f_s=44.1\text{kHz}$ (using CDB8415A)

Figure 4.7 1kHz signal, SDOUT Channel Status Preamble, Start of block, time domain (using CDB8415A)

Figure 4.8 1kHz signal (left channel), analogue out, frequency domain

Figure 4.9 1kHz signal, digital out, frequency domain

Figure 4.10 1kHz signal, SDOUT, frequency domain (using CDB8415A)

4.2 MATLAB, interpolation process

Figure 4.11 Three 20kHz sine waves sampled at $f_s=44.1\text{kHz}$ and quantised to 16 bits (512 samples)

Figure 4.12 Eight times oversampled, linear interpolation using 'interp1' function (4096 samples)

Figure 4.13 Eight times oversampled, standard interpolation using 'interp' function (4096 samples)

Figure 4.14 Eight times oversampled, sinc interpolation (4096 samples)

4.3 SIMULINK Digital Amplifier

Anomaly

On calculation of the SNR of a 16 bit, sampling rate of 44.1kHz, the value was found to be around 98dB. However, on modeling this system on MATLAB SIMULINK the noise floor was about 120dB. This anomaly was then tested with two signals:

1. A digitised 1kHz signal representing +/-0.5 volts (Reference signal)

$$20 \cdot \log(0.5) = -6.02\text{dB}$$

2. A digitised 17.3kHz signal at -98dB down from the reference signal, calculated by

$$-6.02 - 98 = 20 \cdot \log(\text{numerical voltage}) \Rightarrow \text{numerical voltage} = 6.29\mu\text{V}$$

The result is shown in figure 4.15.

Figure 4.15 Normalised Anomaly

Another theory was that the MATLAB system was normalising everything to 1mW. i.e. it might be displaying everything in dBm instead of dB's.

If the SNR = 98dB, the SNR in dBm is:

$$10^{(98/10)} = 6309573444.8$$

$$10 * \log(6309573444.8 / 0.001) = 128 \text{dBm}$$

Now, this calculated value is interesting as the noise value seems to occur at around -120dB.

After repeated engineering efforts to try and overcome the problem found, it was taken to look at the system from the point of view that -120dB was the reference signal to noise ratio.

4.3.1 Single Frequency test

Note that all proceeding results assume the source shown in figure 4.18 with a 90% full-scale 6kHz sine wave.

Figure	Signal	Oversampling	Lineariser	NS	Modulator	Amplifier /demod.
4.16	CD	No	No	No	No	No
4.17	CD	No	No	No	Ramp	Yes
4.18	CD	Lagrange(x8)	5 th order	No	No	No
4.19	CD	Lagrange(x8)	5 th order	5 th order Hawksford	No	No
4.20	CD	Lagrange(x8)	5 th order	5 th order Hawksford	Ramp	Yes
4.21	CD	Lagrange(x8)	5 th order	5 th order optimised	Ramp	Yes
4.22	CD(ext)	Sinc (x8)	5 th order	5 th order optimised	Ramp	Yes
4.23	CD	Lagrange(x8)	9 th order	5 th order optimised	Ramp	Yes
4.24	CD	No	No	No	Sawtooth	Yes
4.25	CD	Lagrange(x8)	5 th order	No	No	No
4.26	CD	Lagrange(x8)	5 th order	5 th order optimised	Sawtooth	Yes

Figure 4.16 16-bit CD player, $f_s = 44.1\text{kHz}$

Figure 4.17 No oversampling/No linearisation/No noise shaping/Ramp PWM

Figure 4.18 Eight times oversampling (Lagrange)/5th order PNPWM lineariser

Figure 4.19 Eight times oversampling (Lagrange)/5th order PNPWM lineariser/Hawksford 5th order NS

Figure 4.20 Eight times oversampling (Lagrange)/5th order PNPWM lineariser/Hawksford 5th order NS/Ramp PWM

Figure 4.21 Eight times oversampling (Lagrange)/5th order PNPWM lineariser/Optimised 5th order NS/Ramp PWM

Figure 4.22 Eight times oversampling (sinc)/5th order PNPWM lineariser/Optimised 5th order NS/Ramp PWM

Figure 4.23 Eight times oversampling (Lagrange)/7th order PNPWM lineariser/Optimised 5th order NS/Ramp PWM

Figure 4.24 No oversampling/No linearisation/No noise shaping/Sawtooth PWM

Figure 4.25 Eight times oversampling (Lagrange)/5th order Dynamic Filter lineariser

Figure 4.26 Eight times oversampling (Lagrange)/5th order Dynamic Filter lineariser/Optimised 5th order NS/Sawtooth PWM

4.3.2 Intermodulation test

Note that all proceeding results assume a 16-bit source, $f_s=44.1\text{kHz}$, with a 45% full scale 11kHz and 12kHz sine wave.

Figure	Signal	Oversampling	Lineariser	NS	Modulator	Amplifier /demod.
4.27	CD	No	No	No	Ramp	Yes
4.28	CD	Lagrange(x8)	5 th order	5 th order optimised	Ramp	Yes
4.29	CD	No	No	No	Sawtooth	Yes
4.30	CD	Lagrange(x8)	5 th order	5 th order optimised	Sawtooth	Yes

Figure 4.27 No oversampling/No linearisation/No noise shaping/Ramp PWM

Figure 4.28 Eight times oversampling (Lagrange)/5th order PNPWM lineariser/Optimised Fifth order NS/Ramp PWM

Figure 4.29 No oversampling/No linearisation/No noise shaping/Sawtooth PWM

Figure 4.30 Eight times oversampling (Lagrange)/5th order Dynamic Filter lineariser/Optimised fifth order NS/Sawtooth PWM

4.33 Single frequency test, time domain

This test aims to show how a 16-bit quantised, $f_s=44.1\text{kHz}$, 6kHz 90% full scale sinusoid is affected in the time domain, when subject to:

- Eight times oversampling
- PNPWM linearisation
- Optimised NS
- Ramp modulation
- Class-D amplification (no gain)
- Demodulation, analogue out

Figure 4.32 Demonstration of signal change when subject to oversampling, linearisation and noise shaping.

Figure 4.33 Demonstration of the creation of pwm from the ramp generator and the noise shaped signal.

Figure 4.34 Demonstration of the class-D amplifier concept and the analogue output stage (post-demodulation).

4.4 Mentor Graphics PCM to PWW mapping

Figure 4.35 PCM to PWW conversion (direct mapping)

4.5 PSPICE PWM conversion

Figure 4.36 Sawtooth generator and PWM system, time domain

Figure 4.37 Sawtooth generator and PWM system, frequency domain

5. DISCUSSION AND EVALUATION

The tests carried out on the Marantz CD-63 CD player and the Crystal Semiconductors CDB8415A interface helped understand the S/PDIF standard and the associated time and frequency domain components thereof.

The figures 4.1 and 4.2 show the analogue output of the CD player for the left and right channels. As expected, the channels were exactly the same voltage at around 6.5 volts peak to peak (pk-pk).

The developed S/PDIF to TTL level circuit shown in figure 3.1 was attached to the digital co-axial output of the CD player. Figure 4.5 clearly shows that the TTL output is within the specified S/PDIF standard of 1V (pk-pk).

The sampling frequency clock can be clearly shown in figure 4.6, with a time period duration of 22.7 μ s. Likewise, the start of a block preamble sequence can be seen in figure 4.7 in the form of 11101000 (CS).

In figure 4.8, the 1kHz signal and 44.1kHz sampling frequency are shown. The noise was found to be approximately 127dBm, which equates to 97dB. This is several dB short of Marantz's quoted figure of 103dB.

Since the bitrate for CD is 2.8224MHz, it would be expected that if a signal comprised of mostly 1's in the digital domain, then there would be a peak at 2.8224MHz showing this. If the signal comprised of mainly 0's, then the peak would be at $\frac{1}{2}$ of the bitrate, i.e. 1.4112MHz. In figure 4.9, the digital signal is at 1kHz and the peak occurs at 1.5MHz, showing that the signal has mainly 0's within it.

The results obtained from using the MATLAB SIMULINK model indicate that 16-bit quality is achievable when using the combination of eight times oversampling, PNPWM linearisation, optimised noise shaping and a ramp modulator (Figures 4.21 and 4.23) Figures 4.21 and 4.22 show little difference in terms of signal to noise ratios to the original 16 bit, fs=44.1kHz signal.

The 2nd and 3rd harmonics for figure 4.21 are at -108dB and -112dB. This compares with figure 4.23, which uses a 7th order lineariser, with the 2nd and 3rd order harmonics at -110dB and -112dB. The use of sinc interpolation does not appear to be as effective as Lagrange's type with the 2nd and 3rd harmonics at -107.3dB and -97.2dB.

This sounds a lot worse than it actually is in reality as the use of Lagrange or Sinc interpolation makes little difference to the overall SNR, but as you can see in the time domain (figures 4.11 to 4.14), the use of a more advanced interpolation method can make a large difference in the perceived reconstruction of the signal. The signal to noise ratio is almost the same as the original CD player with a value of 120dB.

The use and benefit of oversampling and noise shaping is demonstrated in figure 4.19. Here it can be seen that the noise is shifted out of the audible band into the higher frequency bands, which are of in-significant interest. The most effective of the two types of noise shaper was the optimised standard noise shaper which uses Goldberg and Sandler's [2] optimised PWM co-efficients.

The lineariser for PNPWM is shown in figure 4.18. The problem with using no linearisation as shown in figure 4.17 and 4.24 is that there are large 2nd and 3rd order harmonic terms, which need to be eradicated. This is done by introducing the harmonics

that would occur post-PWM before the modulation process. This has the effect that the harmonics are cancelled out after modulation.

The sawtooth method has its own problems. Although the harmonic content is lower in power at the 2nd and 3rd order harmonics, it is more difficult to get rid of them. The proposed Dynamic filter helps to get rid of the harmonics as can be seen in figure 4.26; it does at the same time introduce more noise back into the system as the order of filter increases.

The story continues when using intermodulating tones. The figure 4.27 shows intermodulation distortion for ramp PWM, occurring at 10kHz and 13kHz and the largest at 1kHz.

These distortions have virtually disappeared when using the PNPWM lineariser in figure 4.28.

As before, the sawtooth PWM lineariser (dynamic filtering), gets rid of its associated harmonics from the inherent non-linearity, but at a cost of around an additional 20dB of noise added to the system. This is shown in figure 4.30

The total harmonic distortion at the 2nd and 3rd components for the 7th order PNPWM system in figure 4.23 is:

6kHz signal at magnitude of 1

2nd and 3rd harmonics at -110dB and -112dB corresponding to a total magnitude of 16.3 pico. This is the magnitude of the power, therefore convert to an RMS voltage normalised to a 1Ω resistance.

This gives:

$$P = V^2/R$$

$$V = \sqrt{P} = 4\mu$$

$$V_{rms} = V_{pk}/\sqrt{2} = 2.828 \text{ V}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Multiply by 100 for \% total distortion} &= 0.2828 * 10^{-3} \% \\ &= 0.00028 \% \end{aligned}$$

Note this figure only takes into account the 2nd and 3rd harmonics and that the anomaly, shown in figure 4.15 would account for larger amplitudes of distortion in reference to the normalised 6kHz signal.

The SIMULINK system was monitored in the time domain to identify the processes involved in creating a harmonic free, low noise digital amplifier.

Note that AOUT and BOUT relate to the inverted and non-inverted outputs shown in figures 2.16 and 3.16.

The results of the direct PCM to PWM mapping show the realisation of such a system. These are shown in results 4.35. This was taken a stage further by taking the exact block sequence from the data emulating out of the Crystal Semiconductors board and processing that aswell. Unfortunately, the proceeding simulation did not occur in time for the project deadline.

The final result shows a sawtooth waveform generator and the resulting PWM process. The time domain is shown in figure 4.36, the frequency in 4.37. The components of the

input signal and sawtooth modulator are found within the resultant PWM process (figure 4.37).

6. CRITIQUE

The original objectives set out to achieve in the project specification:

- Analyse and process the PCM hardware interface (S/PDIF) of a CD player.
- Amplify the processed signal via switching techniques in the digital domain using MATLAB for simulation and Mentor Graphics/PSPICE at component level.
- With time permitting, a working hardware design was suggested.
- Outcome of researching the topics.
- Design specification of digital amplifier to be compared with an existing DAC/analogue amplifier solution.
- Results of the investigation into standards for testing and measurement of the digital amplifier.

At the beginning of the project, the task of assigning the allocated budget time to the project was very difficult. This was due to the amount of time required to go to lectures, do assignments, sleep etc.

Looking at what was set to achieve against what has been achieved, the project seems successful. However, this has been at the expense of nearly all of the time outside university available and some of the time to sleep. All of the above tasks w
A massive lesson that has been learned from finishing the project is that, it is very easy to over-specify the amount of work to be completed. The amount of work required to complete this project in full is beyond undergraduate level. It would be much more suited to a thesis [34] at PHD level, perhaps.

Each obstacle that was come across represented a unique engineering challenge in itself.

So much so that the project title should have been called ‘research and evaluate’, rather than ‘design and evaluate’.

The amount of time available to complete the task in hand was not long enough for oneself to be completely happy with the outcome. Around, maybe as much as another year would be required to fully design a hardware solution. Initially, a suggested hardware solution was, with time permitting an objective to be completed. This is an unrealistic task and has been noted. Had an experienced project manager, managed the initial project, he/she would have known what was achievable from one person. This is a lesson that has been learnt. One person can only achieve so much, no matter how many hours are applied. The key to a smooth project schedule is to have an experienced project manager- no question.

The problem with designing such a novel item is that there isn’t a book, which says ‘how to design a digital amplifier’, or such books which contain the fundamentals on the concepts involved. The work is still at a research stage and as such is only found in journals, conferences and other research papers.

After repeated efforts of attempting to get hold of Erik Bresch's thesis [34] on digital amplification, contact was made with the Rose Hulman Institute of technology directly. Progress was made, but unfortunately the thesis arrived two weeks prior to submission of the final report. This discrepancy actually made the progress of research in this field even more frustrating as the work carried out by Bresch was similar to what had already been covered in the interim period. If this had arrived earlier, it would have made sense to take over from where he had left off.

A summary to critically evaluating one's own progress would be that, the project was completed with every resource available and could not of reasonably progressed further. Everything that was in the specification that was expected to be completed within the allocated time was completed; accept for the entire digital amplifier concept using Mentor Graphics.

However, this was due to perceived problems in designing systems such as linearisers and noise shapers in hardware. Having fully designed the system using MATLAB-SIMULINK, it seems that these areas would be implemented using a DSP board in software which would have meant purchasing a electronic product beyond the cost of the allocated budget.

The areas which would work well in an electronic environment were successfully designed in Mentor Graphics, namely PCM to PWM conversion, the class D amplifier and the demodulator.

7. COSTING

• Electronic components for SPDIF/TTL level conversion	= £1.62
• Headers and Crimps for connection to CDB8415A	= £10.69
• Cost of journals/research papers = £0.50*12	= £6.00
	+ cost to the library
• Estimated cost of personal engineering time @£350 a day*	= £350 *60
	= £21,000
• Telephone calls made to Crystal Semiconductors (UK and American offices) and to Rose Hulman Institute of Technology	= £3.55
• Senior lecturers time @ £65 per hour**:	
No.of hours advice $\approx 14 = £65*14$	= £910
TOTAL ESTIMATED COST OF PROJECT	$\approx £21,931$

Estimated realistic cost of any likely product: over £1000

This is due to amount of preliminary research required. The cost of the product to build would be far less dominant in terms of cost in comparison with the cost of the research. This cost would be reduced as time progressed as the costing of the product becomes the dominant term.

* As recommended by School of Engineering's Ian Robinson for a junior engineer

** Approximate hourly wage,inc. university costs as recommended by Dr. Holding

8. CONCLUSIONS/FURTHER WORK

The realisation of a digital amplifier has been limited by yesterday's technology, due to the operational frequency limitation of the output devices.

The MOSFET technology available today would allow, in theory a 16-bit quality output, when used with a CD player source, eight times oversampling using lagrange interpolation, PNPWM linearisation, fifth order optimised noise shaping and modulated using a ramp waveform.

As probably gathered, recommendation of the above system with the proposed practical implementation shown in figure 3.24 is done without hesitation or reservation. This would allow a practical solution to be developed under the constraints of current MOSFET technology for the class-D output stage.

The Dynamic filter method of linearisation for a sawtooth modulator was proposed by Hawksford [4,5]. The solution does not allow 16-bit resolution for the existing constraints put on the system.

The MATLAB SIMULINK model developed allows evaluation of the two main UPWM techniques.

The S/PDIF interface used on most CD players and other PCM sources such as Minidisc and DAT is an over-engineered standard as many of the bits are redundant. It does however provide a convenient way of interfacing with current PCM digital sources.

The perceived problems of the future in the digital amplifier market are that the S/PDIF standard is going to be made redundant as DVD audio and Super Audio Compact Disc (SACD) are not going to have digital outputs at all, due to the copyright protection problems of such implementations.

The proposed solution in chapter 3.7 provides an interesting in-sight into the future of digital amplifier design.

Further improvements will possibly be required into class-D amplification if the Harris HIP4080EVAL2 is anything to go by, as the total harmonic distortion levels of 0.1% are not low enough for the digital CD standards already set at around 0.003%.

It is also interesting to point out that the direct PCM to PWM conversion, shown in figure 10.2 would give rise to no harmonics in the baseband. In that, due to not having a modulator completely eradicates the harmonics occurring in the first place, therefore no lineariser would be required.

8.1 Further work

The work carried out using the direct PCM to PWM mapping theory needs to be simulated with the H-bridge. Both designs are in the appendices, but unfortunately there was not enough time to simulate them.

The proposed solution shown in chapter 3.7 could be followed in order to show whether the theory matches the practical approach. It would be more suitable though as a M.Eng

or PHD project though, as it would involve learning a lot of new concepts with time being the main barrier.

The subject of using feedback in the form of an ADC with several delays may be required to stabilise the H-bridge in practice.

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[ψ]

Web: <http://www.neofidelity.com>

Email: info@neofidelity.com

Web: <http://www.ti.com>

Web: <http://www.cirrus.com>

gevans@crystal.cirrus.com

Web: <http://www.tripath.com>

Email: info@tripath.com

Web: <http://www.audiologic.com>

Email: info@audiologic.com (now part of Cirrus Logic)

10. APPENDICES

Appendix A - MATLAB 'M' programs

```
%*****  
%**David Winter 7.4.01**SIMULINK variables**Parameters.m*****  
%*****  
fs=44.1e3;  
fs_over=8*44.1e3;  
n=8  
% Parameters for Ramp PNPWM lineariser-  
poly_order = 5; %order of approx polynomial  
num_iter = 5; %number of Newton-Raphson iterations  
  
% Parameters Sawtooth  
% Dynamic Filter  
  
filter_order=4;  
fir_length = (filter_order+1);% length of dynamic filter  
mu=22050/(fs_over/2); %i.e. for 8*oversampling mu=0.5, ratio of highest matching  
frequency to nyquist  
nc = (filter_order-2);%no. of co-efficients  
m_target = 0.5;% modulation index  
  
mer=[2.976059 -2.5012 -0.6206618 1.812384 -0.6703392]%Hawksford proposed noise  
shaping co-efficients  
a=1;  
figure(1)  
freqz(mer,a,4096,fs_over)  
  
total_sim_time=0.1  
pause  
sim('source1');  
figure(2)  
[Pxx,w] = PSD(pcm,4096,fs,hanning(4096),2048)  
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));  
subplot 221  
plot(w,Pxx);
```

```

title('PSD(16 bit, 44.1kHz PCM)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
[Pxx,w] = PSD(over,length(over),fs_over,hanning(length(over)),length(over)/2)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
subplot 222
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(8x Oversampled)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
subplot 223
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(8x Oversampled)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
axis([0 20e3 -140 0])

figure(3)
[Pxx,w] = PSD(over1,length(over1),fs_over,hanning(length(over1)),length(over1)/2)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
subplot 221
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(8x Oversampled-matlab interpolation)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
subplot 222
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(8x Oversampled-matlab interpolation)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
axis([0 20e3 -140 0])
[Pxx,w] = PSD(lin,length(lin),fs_over,hanning(length(lin)),length(lin)/2)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
subplot 221
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(Linearizer)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
subplot 222
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(Linearizer)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
axis([0 20e3 -160 0])

```

figure(4)

```

[Pxx,w] = PSD(ns,length(ns),fs_over,hanning(length(ns)),length(ns)/2)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
subplot 221
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(NS)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
subplot 222
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(NS)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
axis([0 20e3 -160 0])
[Pxx,w] = PSD(ns1,length(ns1),fs_over,hanning(length(ns1)),length(ns1)/2)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
subplot 223
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(NS1)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
subplot 224
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(NS1)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
axis([0 20e3 -140 0])

figure(5)
[Pxx,w] = PSD(mod,length(mod),fs_over,hanning(length(mod)),length(mod)/2)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
subplot 221
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(Modulator)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
subplot 222
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(Modulator)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
axis([0 20e3 -140 -110])
[Pxx,w] = PSD(pwm,length(pwm),fs_over,hanning(length(pwm)),length(pwm)/2)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
subplot 223
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(PWM)')

```

```
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
subplot 224
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(PWM)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
axis([0 20e3 -140 0])
```

```
figure(8)
[Pxx,w] =
PSD(analogue1,length(analogue1),fs_over,hanning(length(analogue1)),length(analogue1)
/2)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
subplot 221
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(Digital Amplifier Output-demodulated)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
subplot 222
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(Digital Amplifier Output-demodulated)')
xlabel('Frequency (Hz)')
ylabel('Normalised dB')
axis([0 20e3 -160 0])
```

```

%*****
%lineariser1 *****
%*****
% S-function that linearizes PWM data using the
% PNPWM technique based on a 3rd order polynomial
% Developed from Goldberg/Sandler and Erik Bresch computation*****David
Winter 2001
function [sys,x0,str,ts] = lineariser1(t,x,u,flag,poly_order,num_iter)

% Dispatch the flag. The switch function controls the calls to
% S-function routines at each simulation stage.

switch flag,

    %*****
    % Initialization *
    %*****
    case 0,
        [sys,x0,str,ts]=mdlInitializeSizes(t,x,u,flag,poly_order);% Initialization
        %t,x,u and flag are automatically passed to s-function by Simulink

    %*****
    % Update *
    %*****
    case 2,
        sys = mdlUpdate(t,x,u,poly_order,num_iter);% Update

    %*****
    % Output *
    %*****
    case 3,
        sys = mdlOutputs(t,x,u);% Calculate outputs

    %*****
    % Terminate *

```

```

%*****
case 9,
    sys = [];

otherwise
    error(['unhandled flag = ',num2str(flag)]);% Error handling
end% End of function lineariser1.

%Below are the S-function subroutines that lineariser1.m calls.

%*****
% Function mdlInitializeSizes initializes the states, sample
% times, state ordering strings (str), and sizes structure.
%*****
%
function [sys,x0,str,ts]=mdlInitializeSizes(t,x,u,flag,poly_order)

%prepare all values that have to be stored in the lineariser to be

%states of the s-function
x0= 0.5 * ones(1,(poly_order+1));%creates an array of all ones
%create a new 1-by-poly order+1 matrix out of the the 0.5th element

%initialisation
%For Simulink to recognize an M-file S-function, you must provide it with specific
information about the S-function. This information
%includes the number of inputs, outputs, states, and other block characteristics.
%To give Simulink this information, call the simsizes function at the beginning of
mdlInitializeSizes.
sizes = simsizes;
%This function returns an uninitialized sizes structure. You must load the sizes structure
with information about the S-function.
%See below for the sizes structure fields and description of the information contained in
each field.
sizes.NumContStates = 0;%Number of continuous states
sizes.NumDiscStates = length(x0);%Number of discrete states
sizes.NumOutputs    = 1;%Number of outputs
sizes.NumInputs     = 1;%Number of inputs
sizes.DirFeedthrough = 1;%Flag for direct feedthrough
sizes.NumSampleTimes = 1;%Number of sample times
%After you initialize the sizes structure, call simsizes again.
sys = simsizes(sizes);%This passes the information in the sizes structure to sys, a vector
that holds the information for use by Simulink.
str = [];% No state ordering
ts = [-1 0];% Inherited sample time
%end mdlInitializeSizes

```

```

%*****
% mdlUpdate
% Handle discrete state updates, sample time hits, and major time step
% requirements.
%*****
%
function sys = mdlUpdate(t,x,u,poly_order, num_iter)

%extract data from state vector x
a = [x(1:(length(x)-1))', (u/2+.5)];

%*****
% PNPWM algorithm
%*****

%Step 1: Find coefficients for nth order polynomial

c = polyfit((-floor(poly_order/2):-floor(poly_order/2) + poly_order),a,
poly_order);%(x points,y points,polynomial order)

%floor rounds to nearest integer

%Step 2: Newton-Raphson to find intercept with z=z(t)=t, or y(t)-t = 0

iter_cnt = 0;%initial state of iteration

t_old = 0.5; %initial guess (half way between 0 and 1): i.e. t_est(1) = 0.5

c(length(c)-1) = c(length(c)-1) - 1;

while(iter_cnt < num_iter),

    iter_cnt = iter_cnt+1;%incrementing by 1 each time

    t_new = t_old - (polyval(c,t_old)/polyval(polyder(c),t_old));
    %i.e. t_est(n)-
    polynomial_evaluation_of_t_est(n)/derivative_of_polynomial_evaluation_of_t_est(n)
    %POLYVAL(P,X), when P is a vector of length N+1 whose elements
    %are the coefficients of a polynomial, is the value of the
    %polynomial evaluated at X. i.e. Evaluates polynomial.
    %The polyder function calculates the derivative of polynomials, polynomial products,
    and polynomial quotients.

```

```

    %polyder(p) returns the derivative of the polynomial

    t_old = t_new;%update t_old

end

output_sample = t_new;%assign new name

%store data as states again
sys = [a(2:length(a))'; output_sample];%from 2 to length(a) of array 'a' and output
sample~new time position

%! puts array into column vector.

%end mdlUpdate

%
%*****
% mdlOutputs
% Return the output vector for the S-function (performs calculations)
%*****
%
function sys = mdlOutputs(t,x,u)
%extract and scale the output sample; it's stored in the last state
sys = x(length(x))*2-1;
%end of mdlOutputs

```

```

%*****
%lineariser2*****
%*****

```

```

% S-function that linearises PWM data using the dynamic filtering method.
% Developed from Hawksford and Erik Bresch computation*****David Winter 2001

```

```

function [sys,x0,str,ts] = lineariser2(t,x,u,flag,fir_length,nc,m_target,fs_over,mu)
% Dispatch the flag. The switch function controls the calls to
% S-function routines at each simulation stage.

```

```

switch flag,

```

```

    %*****
    % Initialization *
    %*****
    case 0,
        [sys,x0,str,ts]=mdlInitializeSizes(t,x,u,flag,fir_length,nc,m_target,fs_over,mu);%
        Initialization
        % fir_length = length of dynamic filter = filter order + 1
        % nc = no. of different co-efficients for the individual equalisation FIR filters = Filter
        order -1
        % m_target = modulation index of the target pulse spectrum = 0.5 assumed
        % mu = ratio of the highest matching frequency to the nyquist frequency = (nyquist
        freq./2)/(fs_over/2)

```

```

        %%%%%%%%%%%
        % Update %
        %%%%%%%%%%%
    case 2,
        sys = mdlUpdate(t,x,u,fir_length,nc,m_target,fs_over,mu);

```

```

%%%%%%%%%%
% Output %
%%%%%%%%%%
case 3,
    sys = mdlOutputs(t,x,u,fir_length,nc,m_target,fs_over,mu);

%%%%%%%%%%
% Terminate %
%%%%%%%%%%
case 9,
    sys = [];

otherwise
    error(['unhandled flag = ',num2str(flag)]);
end

%Below are the S-function subroutines that lineariser2.m calls.
%
%*****
% mdlInitializeSizes
% Return the sizes, initial conditions, and sample times for the S-function.
%*****
%
function [sys,x0,str,ts]=mdlInitializeSizes(t,x,u,flag,fir_length,nc,m_target,fs_over,mu)

%prepare all values that have to be stored in the linearizer

%to be states of the s-function
coeff=[zeros(nc-1,fir_length); eye(fir_length); zeros(nc-1,fir_length)];% zeros(m,n)
returns an filter_order-1 by filter_order+1 matrix of zeros.
%eye = identity matrix
input_buffer=0.5*ones(1,fir_length);
output_sample=0.5;

%store all constants as states in the following order:

% -input_buffer

% -columns of the coeff matrix
% -output sample
x0=[input_buffer' ; coeff(:); output_sample];

%do other initialization stuff
sizes = simsizes;

```

%This function returns an uninitialized sizes structure. You must load the sizes structure with information about the S-function.

%See below for the sizes structure fields and description of the information contained in each field.

```
sizes.NumContStates = 0;%Number of continuous states
```

```
sizes.NumDiscStates = length(x0);%Number of discrete states
```

```
sizes.NumOutputs = 1;%Number of outputs
```

```
sizes.NumInputs = 1;%Number of inputs
```

```
sizes.DirFeedthrough = 1;%Flag for direct feedthrough
```

```
sizes.NumSampleTimes = 1;%Number of sample times
```

%After you initialize the sizes structure, call `simsizes` again.

```
sys = simsizes(sizes);%This passes the information in the sizes structure to sys, a vector that holds the information for use by Simulink.
```

```
str = [];% No state ordering
```

```
ts = [-1 0];% Inherited sample time
```

```
%end mdlInitializeSizes
```

```
%
```

```
%*****
```

```
% mdlUpdate
```

```
% Handle discrete state updates, sample time hits, and major time step
```

```
% requirements.
```

```
%*****
```

```
%
```

```
function sys = mdlUpdate(t,x,u,fir_length,nc,m_target,fs_over,mu)
```

```
%prepare all variables/constants used in Hawksford's process
```

```
fstep = mu*(fs_over/2)/(nc-1);
```

```
farg = ((1:nc-1)*fstep)';
```

```
A = farg*(2*pi/fs_over*(1:nc-1));
```

```
A = 2*(cos(A)-1);
```

```
Ainv = inv(A);%find the inverse of
```

```
%extract input_buffer and coeff matrix from state vector x
```

```
input_buffer=x(1:fir_length)';
```

```
coeff=x(fir_length+1:length(x)-1); %Don't forget: the last state
```

```
        %is the output sample
```

```
coeff=reshape(coeff,length(coeff)/fir_length,fir_length);%reshape to a  
length(coeff)/fir_length by fir_length matrix
```

```
%scale and offset input sample value (-1...+1) to the range 0...1
```

```
input_sample= u/2+.5;
```

```
%do filtering:
```

```

%shift coeffs
coeff=coeff(1:((nc-1)+fir_length + (nc-1) -1), 1:(fir_length-1));
coeff=[zeros(1,fir_length-1);coeff];
coeff=[zeros(nc-1+fir_length+nc-1,1),coeff];
coeff(nc,1)=1;
%shift input buffer
input_buffer=[input_sample input_buffer(1:(length(input_buffer)-1))];
for l=1:(fir_length-(nc-1))
    %new xx
    xx=coeff(l+(nc-1),1:fir_length)*input_buffer;% xx must be between 0 and 1

    if xx>1
        disp('Lineariser has been overdriven!');
        xx=1;
    end
    if xx<0
        disp('Lineariser has been overdriven!');
        xx=0;
    end
end

%*****

% uncomment the following line

% to emulate 4097-element coefficient LUTs

%*****

xx = (round(xx*4097))/4097;%Would be used in DSP board

%new coefs on xx
B = sinc(m_target*farg/fs_over)./sinc(xx*farg/fs_over) - 1;%target freq. response
new_coefs=(Ainv*B)';
new_coefs=[(1-2*sum(new_coefs)) new_coefs];

%save new coefs in coeff
coeff(1:l+(nc-1),1)=flipud(new_coefs)';%flipud flips matrices up-down
% i.e. If A is the 2-by-2 matrix,

% A =
% 1 4
% 2 5

% then flipud(A) produces

% 2 5

```

```

% 1 4

coeff(1+(nc-1):1+(nc-1)+(nc-1),l)=new_coefs';

end
%store input_buffer and coeff matrix as states again
sys = [input_buffer'; coeff(:);xx];
%end mdlUpdate

%
%*****
% mdlOutputs
% Return the output vector for the S-function
%*****
%
function sys = mdlOutputs(t,x,u,fir_length,nc,m_target,fs_over,mu)

%extract rescale (to -1...+1) the output sample

sys = x(length(x))*2-1;
%end mdlOutputs

```

```

%*****
%**David Winter 15.2.01**PWM techniques**pwm1.m*****
%*****
clear
close all
clc%clears command window

fin= input('Please input signal frequency (f<=20kHz) (kHz):')
v= input('Please input signal voltage (max=0.5):')
tooth=input('Please input sawtooth=0.5, triangular=1 for modulation type:')
mod_freq=input('Please input sawtooth frequency (Hz):')
fsn=input('Please input n times oversampling fs:')
cutoff=input('Please input low frequency cutoff~rec=60kHz (kHz):')
echo off all

f=fin*1000;
tmax=0.003;%use 2000/f
fs_over=fsn*44.1e3

fs=44.1e3;          %cd player sampling frequency
t=[0:1/fs:tmax]';
n=16;%word length
no_bits=(2^n)-1;%no. of bits
signal=v*sin(2*pi*f*t)%+0.2*sin(2*pi*11e3*t); % signal
t1=[0:1/fs_over:tmax]'; % 5 cycles, new sampling frequency
signal_off=(signal+1e-5*randn(size(t)));% add DITHER
qsignal=fix(signal*no_bits)/no_bits;%16 bit quantised signal***could try round??
figure(1)

```

```

plot(t,qsignal);
title('fs=44.1kHz, 16 bit system');
xlabel('Time (s)')
ylabel('Magnitude (v)')
pause
[Pxx,w] = PSD(qsignal,4096,fs,hanning(4096),2048)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
figure(2)
plot(w,Pxx);
title('Original quantised Signal-PSD')
qsignal=32768+32768*fix(signal*no_bits)/no_bits
pcmstream=dec2bin(qsignal,16)
pause
qsignal=fix(signal*no_bits)/no_bits;% temporary just for producing pcm sequence

signal_interp = interp(qsignal,fsn)
figure(3)
stem(signal_interp,'p');
title('Interpolated Signal-standard');
xlabel('Samples')
ylabel('Magnitude (v)')

pause
[Pxx,w] = PSD(signal_interp,4096,fs_over,hanning(4096),2048)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
figure(4)
plot(w,Pxx);
title('Interpolated Signal-standard-PSD');
pause
signal_interpl=interp1(t,qsignal,t1,'linear')
figure(5)
stem(signal_interpl,'r')
title('Linear Interpolated Signal-standard');
xlabel('Samples')
ylabel('Magnitude (v)')
pause

signal_sincinterp=interpsinc(t1,qsignal,1/fs)
figure(6)
stem(signal_sincinterp,'y')
title('interpolated sinc function');
xlabel('Samples')
ylabel('Magnitude (v)')
pause
[Pxx,w] = PSD(signal_sincinterp,4096,fs_over,hanning(4096),2048)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));

```

```

figure(7)
plot(w,Pxx);
title('interpolated sinc function-psd');
%qsignal2=32768+32768*fix(signal_sincinterp*65536)/65536;
qsignal2=fix(signal_sincinterp*65536)/65536;
var=[t1 qsignal2];
pause
plot(t1,qsignal2)
title('interpolated sinc function');
xlabel('Frequency (Hertz)')
ylabel('Magnitude (v)')
pause

t2=0:1/fs_over:tmax;
saw=0.5*sawtooth(2*pi*mod_freq*t2,tooth);
saw_off=(saw);
figure(8)
plot(t2,saw_off)
title('Sawtooth')
XLABEL('Time(secs)')
YLABEL('Voltage(V)')
pause
[Pxx,w] = PSD(saw_off,4096,fs_over,hanning(4096),2048)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
figure(9)
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(sawtooth)')
pause

pcmstream=dec2bin(qsignal2,16) %interpolated pcm stream
pause
sample=qsignal2>saw_off;
figure(10)
plot(t2,sample)
%axis([0 15e-5 -0.1 1.1])
title('PWM')
XLABEL('Time(secs)')
YLABEL('Digital State')
pause
[Pxx,w] = PSD(sample,4096,fs_over,hanning(4096),2048)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
figure(11)
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(PWM)')
pause
sampleamp=sample*5;

```

```

figure(12)
plot(t2,sampleamp)
%axis([0 15e-5 -0.1 5.1])
title('PWM amplified')
XLABEL('Time(secs)')
YLABEL('Digital State')
pause
[Pxx,w] = PSD(sampleamp,4096,fs_over,hanning(4096),2048)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
figure(13)
plot(w,Pxx);
title('PSD(PWM amplified)')
pause
%Filtering
wn = (cutoff*1e3)*2/fs_over;%- i.e. max normalised to fs, wn between 0-1
n=4;
nfft=1024;
[b,a] = butter(n,wn);
[h,w,s]=freqz(b,a,nfft,fs_over);
s.plot = 'both'; % Plot the magnitude only.
s.xunits = 'hz'; % Label the frequency units correctly.
s.yunits = 'dB'; % Plot the magnitude dB
figure(14)
freqzplot(h,w,s); %i.e. plot((w),10*log(abs(h)));
title('Butterworth filtered')
pause
Rp=0.001;
[b1,a1] = cheby1(n,Rp,wn)
[h1,w1,s1]=freqz(b1,a1,nfft,fs_over);
s.plot = 'both'; % Plot the magnitude only.
s.xunits = 'khz'; % Label the frequency units correctly.
s.yunits = 'dB'; % Plot the magnitude dB
figure(15)
freqzplot(h1,w1,s1); %i.e. plot((w),10*log(abs(h)));
title('Chebyshev filtered')
pause
Rp=0.001
Rs=60
[b2,a2]=ellip(n,Rp,Rs,wn);
[h2,w2,s2]=freqz(b2,a2,nfft,fs_over);
s.plot = 'both'; % Plot the magnitude only.
s.xunits = 'khz'; % Label the frequency units correctly.
s.yunits = 'dB'; % Plot the magnitude dB
figure(16)
freqzplot(h2,w2,s2); %i.e. plot((w),10*log(abs(h)));
title('ellip filtered')

```

```

pause

% FIR design
fc=(cutoff*1e3);
transition=500;
passripple=0.001;
stopatt=60;
% Putting in quoted corner frequency causes too early cutoff
% Moving corner frequency halfway into transition region improves things
fc=fc+transition/2;
% Filter specification is for a Kaiser window
deltapass=10^(passripple/20)-1;
deltastop=10^(-stopatt/20);
delta=min([deltapass deltastop]);
Amp=-20*log10(delta);

N=ceil((Amp-7.95)/(14.36*transition/fs_over));
if Amp <= 21
    beta=0;
else
    beta=0.5842*((Amp-21)^0.4) + 0.07886*(Amp-21);
end
b3=fir1(N-1,2*fc/fs_over,kaiser(N,beta));
a3=1;
[h,f]=freqz(b3,a3,1024,fs_over);
% If you want a plot with a lin frequency axis
figure(17)
plot(f,20*log10(abs(h)))
% If you want a plot with a log frequency axis
%semilogx(f,20*log10(abs(h)))
set(gca,'xgrid','on','ygrid','on');
xlabel('Frequency (Hertz)')
ylabel('Magnitude Response (dB)')
set(gcf,'Name','Fir filter')
figure(gcf)
pause

sig = filter(b,a,sampleamp);
figure(19)
plot(t2,sig);
title('PWM-Butterworth filtered')
pause
sig1 = filter(b1,a1,sampleamp);
figure(20)
plot(t2,sig1,'r');
title('PWM-Chebyshev filtered')

```

```

pause
sig2 = filter(b2,a2,sampleamp);
figure(21)
plot(t2,sig2,'k');
title('PWM-ellip filtered')
pause
sig3 = filter(b3,a3,sampleamp);
figure(22)
plot(t2,sig3,'m');
title('PWM-FIR filtered')

a=fft(sig);
f=[0:length(a)-1]*fs_over/length(a);
a1=fft(sig1);
f1=[0:length(a1)-1]*fs_over/length(a1);
a2=fft(sig2);
f2=[0:length(a2)-1]*fs_over/length(a2);
a3=fft(sig3);
f3=[0:length(a3)-1]*fs_over/length(a3);

pause
figure(23)
title('fft(PWM filtered)')
x=6e7;%CO-ORDINATES for text
y=230;
y1=210;
y2=190;
y3=170;
text(x,y,'blue=butterworth')
text(x,y1,'red=chebyshev')
text(x,y2,'green=elliptical')
text(x,y3,'cyan=FIR')
hold on;
plot(f,20*log(abs(a)));
plot(f1,20*log(abs(a1)),'r');
plot(f2,20*log(abs(a2)),'g');
plot(f3,20*log(abs(a3)),'c');
zoom on
hold off
pause
[Pxx,w] = PSD(sig,4096,fs_over,hanning(4096),2048)
Pxx=10*log10(Pxx/max(Pxx));
figure(24)
plot(w,Pxx);
title('psd(final)')
pause

```

```

%*****
%EIA-560 standards - [signals.m] - David Winter, B.Eng ESIE Final year 2001*
%Frequency response+intermodulation signal tones (*.wav)*****
*****

clear
close all
echo off

fs = 44.1e3
t=0:1/fs:10;
f=4;

left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);

% Make each signal a column vector. These statements
% have no effect on left and right if they start out as
% column vectors, it will transpose the vectors if they
% started out as row vectors.
left=left(:);
right=right(:);

```

```

% Remove any DC terms
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);

% Normalize the signals to +/- 1
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;

% Make a stereo matrix ('n' columns, i.e. 2 in stereo, a left and right)
stereo=[left right];

% Produce sound output
sound(stereo,fs,16);

% Generate wav file
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\4Hz');
pause

f=8;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\8Hz');
pause

f=16;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];

```

```
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\16Hz');
pause
```

```
f=32;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\32Hz');
pause
```

```
f=63;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\63Hz');
pause
```

```
f=125;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
```

```
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\125Hz');  
pause
```

```
f=250;  
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);  
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);  
left=left(:);  
right=right(:);  
left=left-mean(left);  
right=right-mean(right);  
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));  
left=left/k;  
right=right/k;  
stereo=[left right];  
sound(stereo,fs,16);  
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\250Hz');  
pause
```

```
f=500;  
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);  
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);  
left=left(:);  
right=right(:);  
left=left-mean(left);  
right=right-mean(right);  
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));  
left=left/k;  
right=right/k;  
stereo=[left right];  
sound(stereo,fs,16);  
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\500Hz');  
pause
```

```
f=1e3;  
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);  
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);  
left=left(:);  
right=right(:);  
left=left-mean(left);  
right=right-mean(right);  
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));  
left=left/k;  
right=right/k;  
stereo=[left right];  
sound(stereo,fs,16);  
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\1kHz');
```

```
pause

f=2e3;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\2kHz');
pause
```

```
f=4e3;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\4kHz');
pause
```

```
f=8e3;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\8kHz');
pause
```

```
f=10e3;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\10kHz');
pause
```

```
f=12.5e3;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\12k5Hz');
pause
```

```
f=16e3;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\16kHz');
pause
```

```

f=18e3;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\18kHz');
pause

```

```

f=20e3;
left=sin(2*pi*f*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\20kHz');
pause

```

```

%Intermodulation distortion
f1=60;
f2=7e3;;
left=sin(2*pi*f1*t)+sin(2*pi*f2*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f1*t)+sin(2*pi*f2*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\60Hz+7kHz');

```

pause

```
f1=11e3;
f2=12e3;
left=sin(2*pi*f1*t)+sin(2*pi*f2*t);
right=sin(2*pi*f1*t)+sin(2*pi*f2*t);
left=left(:);
right=right(:);
left=left-mean(left);
right=right-mean(right);
k=max(max(abs(left)),max(abs(right)));
left=left/k;
right=right/k;
stereo=[left right];
sound(stereo,fs,16);
wavwrite(stereo,fs,16,'d:\11kHz+12kHz');
```

```
*****
****Sinc function utilised in pwm1.m****interpsinc.m*****
*****
%INTERPSINC Interpolate a sampled function using sin(x)/x (a.k.a. sinc function)
% yi = INTERPSINC(xi,f,xd,nref,nrefx)
% Use the sinc function to interpolate the function
% f(x) sampled at regular intervals to the points xi
% xi are the x values to which you want to interpolate, can be any nd-array
% f is a vector of values of f(x) evaluated at evenly spaced intervals
% if f is not a row or column vector a warning is
% issued and the data is vectorized by columns
% xd is the sample spacing of the elements of f
% optional, assumed to be 1 if not present
% nref is the reference element of vector f,
% optional, assumed to be zero if omitted
```

```

% (the first element of f is labeled element 1)
% nrefx is the x value assigned to element nref
% optional, assumed to be 0 if omitted
%
% If all three arguments are omitted the vector f is assumed to be f(x) evaluated
% at x=1,2,3 ... length(f)
%
% EXAMPLE, interpolate values for a sine wave sampled at twice Nyquist frequency

% f=sin(0:pi/4:20*pi) % "f" is a vector of samples of a sine wave sampled every pi/4
% radians (90 degrees)
% interp([71/8*pi:pi/4:89/8*pi],f,pi/4,1,0) % estimate sine wave at some points halfway
% between samples
% sin([71/8*pi:pi/4:89/8*pi]) % compare to true value of sine waves at these points

%REF: Discrete-Time Signal Processing, Oppenheim and Schaffer, 1999

function yi = interpsinc(xi,f,varargin)
% Use cell array varargin to set optional input values xd, nref and nrefx
d={1,0,0};d(1:length(varargin))=varargin;
xd=d{1};nref=d{2};nrefx=d{3};
%convert xi from units of x to fractional index values
ni=nref+(xi-nrefx)/xd;
% convert ni to a row vector
ni=ni(:)';
% convert f to a row vector
if prod(size(f))>max(size(f));
    warning('input function "f" is not a vector, will vectorize by columns')
end
f=f(:)';
% Check to see if some requested interpolation points are outside the range of the
% sampled function
if min(ni)<1|max(ni)>length(f)
    %warning('some points are outside the range of the input function,')
    %warning('you are EXTRAPOLATING not INTERPOLATING, results are likely to
    stink!')
end
% create interpolation weights using the sinc function
NI=sinc([1:length(f)]'*ones(size(ni))-ones(size(f))*ni);
% create interpolated values
yi=f*NI;
% convert answer (yi) back to original shape of input xi
yi=reshape(yi,size(xi));

```


Figure 10.2 PCM to PWM conversion

Figure 10.3 16-bit shift register (within symbol)

Figure 10.4 16-bit storage register (within symbol)

Figure 10.5 PCM to PWM conversion (left channel) with S/PDIF block/frame format

Figure 10.6 PCM to PWM conversion (right channel) with S/PDIF block/frame format

Figure 10.7 H-Bridge class-D amplifier and demodulator

Appendix D - Further maths for Dynamic filter method

A brief investigation of the UPWM-inherent nonlinearities is necessary to understand the dynamic filtering method. It is easiest to find the origin of the nonlinear behaviour by comparing a PCM signal, which is free of harmonics, and a PWM signal generated by direct amplitude-to-pulse-width mapping from the same PCM signal, keeping in mind that the demodulation in both cases is done by low-pass filtering. This comparison is done on a sample-by-sample basis in the frequency domain. Recall the Fourier transform for a rectangular pulse is:

Figure 10.8 Fourier Transform for a rectangular pulse

Now consider a three-sample PCM-sequence and a three-sample PWM-sequence and the Fourier transforms of each individual pulse:

Figure 10.9 PCM-PWM Spectra Comparison

As is apparent from the above equation and Figure 10.9, the transfer function of a PCM system is constant, since each PCM sample has the same spectrum, which is only amplitude scaled. The individual PWM samples, however, have different Fourier transforms with respect to amplitude and frequency scaling. Therefore, a PWM system can be thought of as a PCM system with a time-varying transfer function. In order to linearise the PWM system, an equalising filter is needed that compensates the sample-dependent changes. The transfer function of this filter would, therefore, have to change from sample to sample, forcing the overall transfer characteristic to be constant at least in the audio baseband. This is depicted in Figure 10.10.

Figure 10.10 Frequency Domain Analysis of Dynamic PWM-Linearisation

Each sample has its own 4th -order FIR equalisation filter, whose magnitude response would have to be the approximate inverse of the PWM sample's frequency spectrum, such that product of both is unity, at least in the audio band. However, following Hawksford, a flat overall response will not be targeted, but the spectrum that corresponds to 50% duty cycle PWM-pulse.

Each of those sample specific 4th -order FIR equalisation filters has a dispersive response, affecting the two previous and the two following PWM-samples, thereby changing their values and then their associated equalisation filters, which affect the initial PWM sample again. It is obvious that the sample-based equalisation method relies on a convergence after a certain number of iteration steps. Therefore, a number of samples and their specific equalisation filters interact to produce the overall dynamic PWM linearising filter.

Filter design

The filter is designed in order to change accordingly, whereby the impulse response of the FIR correction filter is obtained from the inverse Fourier transform of the PWM's spectrum.

The transfer function of the filter is:

$$TF_F(f) = c_0 + 2*c_1*\cos(2*\Pi*(f/f_{NY})) + 2*c_2*\cos(4*\Pi*(f/f_{NY}))$$

Equation 10.1

Where $c_0 + 2*c_1 + 2*c_2$ are the various co-efficients equal to one for unity (dc)

f = applied frequency (Hz)

f_{NY} = Nyquist frequency (Hz)

To ensure correct DC equalisation, the sum of the co-efficients needs to be at unity:

$$1 = c_0 + 2*c_1 + 2*c_2$$

Equation 10.2

such that the frequency response of the FIR filter becomes:

$$TF_F(f) = 1 + 2*c_1(\cos(2*\Pi*(f/f_{NY}))-1) + 2*c_2(\cos(4*\Pi*(f/f_{NY}))-1)$$

Equation 10.3

The frequency spectrum of the PWM samples to be corrected utilises a sinc function, where the normalised frequency spectrum of the PWM sample $x(n)$ to be equalised is:

$$TF_{PWM} = \text{sinc}(x(n)*T_c*f)$$

Equation 10.4

$x(n)$ = PWM sample to be sampled (0 to 1, with 1 representing 1 maximum pulse width)_

T_c = Pulse width (s)

f = applied frequency (Hz)

However as Hawksford [4,5] points out, for this method to be 100% accurate, an infinite amount of co-efficients would be required, thus an approximation is made. The magnitude response corresponds to a 50% duty cycle PWM pulse, i.e. PWM pulse length of $0.5*T_c$.

$$\Rightarrow T(f) = \text{sinc}(0.5*T_c*f) \text{ for } 0 \text{ to } 20\text{kHz}$$

Equation 10.5

Therefore chose a modulation index of 0.5.

The co-efficients of the FIR filter have to be determined such that in the frequency band for which linearisation has to be attained:

$$TF_F(f)*TF_{PWM} = T(f) \text{ from } 0 \text{ to } 20\text{kHz}$$

Equation 10.6

This can be solved using any optimisation technique such as normal equations, Gram-Schmidt orthogonalisation etc. An accurate way is to force the equality of the equalised pulse spectrum and the target spectrum at only two points (matching frequencies), e.g. $f_{match1} = f_{max}/2$ and $f_{match2} = f_{max}$.

This can be written as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} 2(\cos(2\pi(f_{match1}/fc)) - 1) & 2(\cos(4\pi(f_{match1}/fc)) - 1) \\ 2(\cos(2\pi(f_{match2}/fc)) - 1) & 2(\cos(4\pi(f_{match2}/fc)) - 1) \end{bmatrix} \bullet \begin{bmatrix} C1 \\ C2 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\text{sinc}(0.5Tcf_{match1})}{\text{sinc}(x(n)Tcf_{match1})} - 1 \\ \frac{\text{sinc}(0.5Tcf_{match2})}{\text{sinc}(x(n)Tcf_{match2})} - 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Equation 10.7

Using this equation C1 and C2 can be solved. Finally C0 can be calculated using the DC constraint.

Dynamic linearising filter

The structure of this system is shown in matrix form of fifth order.

$$\begin{bmatrix} C0f & C1e & C2d & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ C1f & C0e & C1d & C2c & 0 & 0 \\ C2f & C1e & C0d & C1c & C2b & 0 \\ 0 & C2e & C1d & C0c & C1b & C2a \\ 0 & 0 & C2d & C1c & C0b & C1a \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C2c & C1b & C0a \end{bmatrix} \bullet \begin{bmatrix} IPf \\ IPe \\ IPd \\ IPc \\ IPb \\ IPa \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} OPf \\ OPe \\ OPd \\ OPc \\ OPb \\ OPa \end{bmatrix}$$

Equation 10.8

- Step 1: The process starts with the calculation of OPf. Next, the co-efficients Cxf are calculated from OPf using equation 10.7. and take place in the left most column of the co-efficient matrix. Then OPe is calculated and the new Cxe is found. The new co-efficients take their place in the co-efficient matrix. This procedure is repeated for OPd and OPc. Finally, OPa is evaluated, which forms the output of the lineariser.
- Step 2: The c-matrix is diagonally shifted, where only the uppermost left new element of the c-matrix is set to one, all other elements are set to zero. Also, the op-matrix is shifted down. A zero is shifted into the top most position. The ip-matrix is shifted down and a new PCM input sample IPg takes the top most position. The matrix is shown in equation 10.9.

$$\begin{bmatrix}
 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & C0f & C1e & C2d & 0 & 0 \\
 0 & C1f & C0e & C1d & C2c & 0 \\
 0 & C2f & C1e & C0d & C1c & C2b \\
 0 & 0 & C2e & C1d & C0c & C1b \\
 0 & 0 & 0 & C2d & C1c & C0b
 \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix}
 IPg \\
 IPf \\
 IPe \\
 IPd \\
 IPc \\
 IPb
 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix}
 0 \\
 OPf \\
 OPe \\
 OPd \\
 OPc \\
 OPb
 \end{bmatrix}$$

Equation 10.9

A final note to add regarding the design of the filter is that it requires oversampling of at least a factor of four for good results [34].

